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Performance Optimization in Accelerator Libraries using Parameter-Tuning

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Abstract

This thesis contributes to the field of performance-portable computation by introducing an auto-tuning framework in alpaka 3, a C++ library that enables platform-independent heterogeneous accelerator programming. It attempts to enhance alpaka's performance portability by maximizing resource utilization across hardware platforms and minimizing the time consumption of manual tuning for individual problem descriptions. More specifically, the proposed auto-tuning mechanism allows dynamically adjusting performance-critical parameters during production runs. The tuning-mechanism is platform-aware and tracks performance measurements and tuning characteristics with respect to the underlying architecture. alpaka 3 implements a special programming model that allows domain-specific problem descriptions independent of the number of physical workers. This model enables performance-critical parameters, such as grid size and thread-block size, to be subject to the optimization process without violating the correctness of the algorithm. While this provides a general mechanism for tuning alpaka 3 kernels, the proposed tuning framework goes further by allowing both custom runtime and compile-time parameters to be involved in the tuning process. This offers users a fine-grained approach to optimizing specific algorithms.

This thesis first introduces the architectural features of the platforms used for evaluation—including GPUs from AMD and NVIDIA, and an AMD microprocessor—to develop a clearer understanding of the specific hardware resources targeted by the proposed auto-tuning mechanism. We then review and classify related auto-tuning frameworks to contextualize our approach. Following this, we describe the design and implementation of our tuning mechanism, which has been integrated into alpaka. The results are validated using a collection of commonly used benchmarks and a scientific clustering algorithm under varying workloads.

Zusammenfassung

Diese Arbeit leistet einen Beitrag im Bereich der heterogenen Programmierung durch die Einführung eines Auto-Tuning-Frameworks in alpaka 3, einer C++-Bibliothek, die plattformunabhängige Programmierung ermöglicht. Ziel ist es, die Performance-Portabilität von alpaka zu verbessern, indem die Ressourcenauslastung über verschiedene Hardwareplattformen hinweg maximiert und der zeitliche Aufwand für manuelles Tuning spezifischer Problemstellungen minimiert wird. Der vorgestellte Auto-Tuning-Mechanismus erlaubt es insbesondere, leistungsrelevante Parameter dynamisch zur Laufzeit anzupassen. Der Mechanismus erfasst Charakteristiken zu diesen Parametern in Bezug auf die zugrunde liegende Architektur. alpaka 3 implementiert ein spezielles Programmiermodell, das domänenspezifische Problembeschreibungen unabhängig von der Anzahl physischer Recheneinheiten erlaubt. Dieses Modell ermöglicht es, leistungsrelevante Parameter wie Grid-Größe und Thread-Block-Größe in den Optimierungsprozess einzubeziehen, ohne die Korrektheit des Algorithmus zu beeinträchtigen. Während dies bereits einen allgemeinen Mechanismus zur Optimierung von alpaka-3-Kernen darstellt, geht das vorgeschlagene Framework darüber hinaus, indem es zusätzlich sowohl benutzerdefinierte Laufzeit- als auch Kompilierzeit-Parameter unterstützt. Dies ermöglicht eine feingranulare Optimierung spezifischer Algorithmen.

Zunächst werden die Architekturen der Plattformen vorgestellt, welche für die Evaluierung der Ergebnisse verwendet werden – darunter GPUs von AMD und NVIDIA sowie ein Mikroprozessor von AMD – um ein besseres Verständnis für die zugrunde liegenden Hardware-Ressourcen zu entwickeln, auf die der Auto-Tuning-Mechanismus abzielt. Anschließend werden bestehende Auto-Tuning-Frameworks klassifiziert und eingeordnet, um den eigenen Ansatz kontextuell zu begründen. Im weiteren Verlauf werden das Design und die Implementierung des entwickelten Tuning-Mechanismus beschrieben, der in alpaka integriert wurde. Die Wirksamkeit des Frameworks wird schließlich anhand einer Sammlung kleinerer Benchmarks und eines wissenschaftlichen Clustering-Algorithmus validiert.

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1 Introduction and Motivation

Parallel computing is a cornerstone of modern high-performance computing (HPC) environments. It is the driving force behind large-scale simulations, machine learning models, and big data analytics. Modern supercomputers listed in the annual Top500 report [1], which contains a list of the best-performing HPC systems ranked by their peak floating-point performance, are designed to distribute these workloads across multiple computing nodes. As an example, the biggest European supercomputer Alps [2] ranked 7th in the 2024 Top500 report, with its relatively compact design still occupying an area of 117 square meters of floor space for server-housing racks alone. It provides access to a total of 4008 nodes that will be selected based on the individual requirements of the scientific workloads. By improving upon the resource utilization of the provided architectures, large-scale simulations or data analysis might decrease the required number of nodes, thus increasing data locality and efficiency both in terms of compute time and energy. Recent developments show that energy efficiency is an important factor in the context of HPC; as low efficiency leads to higher operational costs along with sustainability concerns [3]. And while efficiency has also been shown to increase [4], considering the development of the FLOP-per-watt ratios of the aforementioned Top500 collection, it is still outpaced by the increasing computational demands as the total energy consumption increases rapidly. According to [5] (page 5), the energy consumption of data centers (including HPC systems, cloud service providers and enterprise infrastructures) has increased over 100% from 2018 to 2023 in the US. Tröpgen et al. [6] conducted an analysis of the CPU-SPEC benchmark [7], where they compared power consumption for microprocessors over the span of 16 years. The authors concluded *“While there are certainly physical limitations to this growth [in power consumption], they are not yet visible in the data.”*

This growing energy demand underscores the need not only for performance but also for efficient and adaptable use of heterogeneous hardware resources. Usually, HPC environments provide access to several architectures which differ in terms of hardware capabilities, vendors, and programming interfaces such as CUDA for NVIDIA GPUs or HIP for AMD GPUs. Restricting an HPC software to only one hardware vendor has significant shortcomings in terms of long-term maintainability, leveraging upcoming technologies, and resource utilization in heterogeneous systems. A heterogeneous platform could, for example, consist of a field-programmable gate array (FPGA) to handle specialized tasks coupled with a graphics accelerator and a host [8].

Heterogeneous programming libraries such as Kokkos [9], alpaka [10] or its successor alpaka [11] try to achieve the desired portability by providing an abstraction interface that allows for a single code to be compatible with varying hardware devices. The SYCL [12] framework is another approach to allow portability across different hardware platforms, which provides its own programming model. A unified and portable interface might come at the cost of performance, because of the hardware-agnostic nature of a problem description given by the user. While it has been shown [13], that hardware abstraction libraries can achieve reasonable performance compared to a native library implementation, they cannot guarantee that parallel programs that are implemented using such an abstraction interface are fully optimized to utilize the underlying computational resources.

Fine-tuning an application to make efficient use of the platform’s capabilities usually involves taking into account vendor-specific information presented through profiling tools such as NVIDIA’s Nsight Compute CLI (nvcc). This process can become very time-inefficient for the developer, since it usually strongly depends on the workload in addition to the underlying hardware architecture and therefore has to be manually adjusted for each application. Optimal execution configurations tend to vary significantly across different memory layouts, thread execution models, and processing units.

The choice of configuration parameters such as the number of threads and thread-blocks is a critical aspect of resource utilization. Therefore, alpaka introduces an abstraction layer that allows the user to

describe a problem independent of these parameters, making them applicable to the tuning process while maintaining the correctness of the program. To optimize the performance of a kernel, such as simple matrix multiplication, methods such as tiling are used to increase memory locality and arithmetic intensity. The optimal size for tiling is not fixed and depends on the input size of the matrix. Highly optimized libraries such as cuBLAS [14] provided directly by NVIDIA select a kernel-specific tiling size based on the extent of the problem. Tiling size is therefore a fitting example for a problem-specific tuning parameter.

This thesis introduces an automated tuning framework integrated into alpaka. This framework was designed to automate the process of finding optimal parameter configurations and optimize performance portability across various hardware architectures and problem descriptions. alpaka allows targeting several back-ends such as CUDA[15], HIP[16] and SYCL[12], supporting execution on multiple different underlying architectures. This work aims to optimize the performance of a problem description based on information provided by the hardware vendors and by evaluating simulated kernel executions.

The user will be able to specify the parameters that should be involved in the tuning process and has the option to give hints about the tuning space of each parameter. Each tuning parameter introduces another dimension in the search space that encompasses all possible combinations of tuning parameters. A brute-force exploration that tests every possible combination is, therefore, in most cases, infeasible. Hence, local search or model-based optimization methods are used in state-of-the-art tuning frameworks [17, 18, 19]. For example, Bayesian optimization is a widely adopted strategy to approximate an optimum for a given black-box function that is difficult to express in a closed mathematical form. It is commonly used for hyperparameter optimization in the field of machine learning to maximize the model’s accuracy and minimize the duration of its training [20].

Local search strategies are used to identify promising regions within the tuning space, where iterative refinement can quickly converge to a near-optimal solution. Simulated annealing is compared to naive random search and brute-force strategies.

We begin by providing background information on parallel computing and the architectural differences between major hardware vendors, including AMD, NVIDIA, and general-purpose CPUs. We also introduce the alpaka library, the main ecosystem on which the proposed tuning mechanism is built. Following this, we present an overview of related work in the field of autotuning, classifying existing tuning frameworks and notable contributions with respect to their optimization objectives and methods. We then describe the design and implementation of our own auto-tuning framework, which is integrated into alpaka. This includes details on the selection of parameter spaces, the search strategy and general software design. To evaluate the effectiveness of our approach, we apply the framework to several benchmark problems — including the *PoissonEquation*, *BabelStream*, *HeatEquation*, and the *CLUE* clustering algorithm — and analyze the resulting performance gains. We conclude by discussing the implications of our results and outlining possible directions for future work.

2 Background

The general aim of the upcoming chapter is to introduce the reader to the environment in which the alpaka library is actively used. It provides a motivation for parallel computation and presents various forms of parallelism 2.1 which can be adopted for parallel applications.

Afterwards, parallel computing devices from various hardware vendors are presented 2.2,2.3,2.4, showcasing architectural design decisions. The concretely examined systems are later used in the experimental Chapter 5. alpaka can target each of these systems via their respective software back-end (CPU – OpenMP, NVIDIA – CUDA, AMD – HIP/ROCm, Intel – SYCL).

Each of these software back-ends is introduced individually, followed by an explanation of how alpaka abstracts over them to provide a unified programming model. Subsequently, the key concepts alpaka and the naming conventions are presented 2.5, as these are essential for understanding the implementation and the later chapters.

In the Strategy Section 3.4, several fundamental concepts—such as tuning spaces and search strategies—are introduced to prepare the reader for the implementation chapter. With this theoretical background of tuning in place, we then review related approaches from the literature 2.8.

2.1 Parallel computing devices

Moore's Law [22] which predicts a doubling of the transistor count every two years (although this number varies depending on the sources), continues to be active [23, p. 2] and a driving force behind advances in the semiconductor industry [24]. While transistor counts continue to rise, corresponding performance gains are no longer achieved through higher clock frequencies. As shown in Figure 2.1, clock rates have remained largely constant over the past two decades. In the early 2000s, attempts to push the frequencies

Figure 2.1: Clock rate progression on microprocessors from 1978 to 2012. Figure from [p. 24] Hennessy and Patterson [21].

higher led to disproportionate increases in energy demand and significant challenges in heat dissipation, as higher leakage currents and voltage requirements required advanced cooling solutions [25]. As a result, further scaling of the clock frequency became unsustainable in terms of both performance-per-watt and cost [24]. Figure 2.1 illustrates this trend: after 2003, clock rates stagnated, shifting from rapid logarithmic growth to a barely increasing 50% over the next 15 years. This practical limit—where power and thermal constraints prevent further frequency scaling—is commonly referred to as the *Power Wall* [26].

The trend to scale hardware performance and utilize the increasing number of transistors predicted by *Moore's Law* has been the introduction of various forms of parallelism - some of them saw their invention in the 20th century and have long been an integral part of microprocessor- and (to a certain extent) accelerator design, yet they continue to evolve with recent innovations. Other advances such as the switch to multi-core architectures [27] and the introduction of general-purpose GPUs [28] were necessary to satisfy the higher computational demands while crucial scaling factors such as single-thread performance showed signs of stagnation.

Forms of Parallelism: Instruction-Level to Thread-Level

The following section provides a brief overview of key techniques and forms of parallelism that emerged to overcome the limitations imposed by the previously discussed *Power Wall*[26]. High-performance computing (HPC) systems typically combine multiple parallelism paradigms—including instruction-level, data-level, thread-level, and task-level parallelism—to maximize resource utilization and enable scalable computation across modern hardware platforms. Many scientific simulations and other compute-intensive HPC workloads depend on the coordinated use of these paradigms to fully exploit the available computational resources in large-scale data center environments. Figure 2.2 illustrates major advances in parallel programming and hardware architectures from 1960 to 2025, several of which are discussed in the following sections. For a more comprehensive treatment of these concepts, we refer the reader to Hennessy and Patterson [21].

Instruction-Level Parallelism

Instruction-Level Parallelism (ILP) allows the execution of multiple commands from a single stream of instructions in parallel. Foundational techniques include *pipelining*, which was first introduced in

Figure 2.2: Timeline (1960 - 2025) highlighting relevant advances to hardware and parallel programming models with regards to parallel computation.

IBM Stretch [29] (released 1961). Pipelining allows instruction stages (fetch, decode, execute, etc.) to overlap, which allows multiple instructions residing in different stages of the Pipeline to be executed in parallel in order to improve throughput. The traditional pipeline steps that still exist in some form (although frequently composed of multiple sub-stages) are *Instruction Fetch (IF)*, *Instruction Decode (ID)*, *Execute (EX)*, *memory access (MEM)* and *write-back (WB)*. Detailed illustrations and explanations of this architectural concept and parallelization scheme can be found in [21, Appendix C]. Modern microprocessors often feature multiple units for each stage of the pipeline.

An additional hardware feature that complements a wide instruction pipeline is the execution of *out-of-order*. It enables the dynamic reordering of instructions at runtime to improve the utilization of functional units (as multiple fetch, decode and execution units may exist). Since instructions can vary in execution cycles, because of delays introduced by memory accesses, data dependencies or instruction type - reordering reduces pipeline stalls and increases memory throughput. A more detailed view on out-of-order execution is provided on [21, page 143].

An alternative yet less common approach first introduced in 1983 [30] is the use of *Very Long Instruction Word (VLIW)* architectures to take advantage of ILP by introducing compiler-managed parallelism where multiple instructions are issued into a single bundle [21, p. 121].

Data-Level Parallelism

Data-Level Parallelism (DLP) exploits the fact that the same operation can be applied across large data sets. This form of parallelism is typically realized through *Single Instruction, Multiple Data (SIMD)*, where a single instruction operates on multiple data elements in parallel [31, ch. 2]. This type of instruction was first introduced to x86 architectures via Intel Pentium MMX in 1997 [32], featured 64-bit wide registers for parallel data operations. Early vector processors such as the ILLIAC IV [33] introduced SIMD at the hardware level, and modern processors extend this with SIMD instruction sets such as Intel's SSE/AVX and ARM's NEON [21, pp. 281–285][34]. SIMD instructions necessitate specialized hardware units, often referred to as vector units, which are capable of executing the same operation across multiple data elements in parallel within a single instruction cycle [31, ch. 2]. In addition to the ability to process wide vector registers with multiple data elements, modern vector units often support specialized instructions such as the Fused Multiply-Add (FMA), which effectively perform two operations (multiplication and addition) per cycle and data element.

Thread-Level Parallelism

Thread-Level Parallelism (TLP) refers to the concurrent execution of multiple independent instruction streams—i.e., threads—across multiple processing elements [31, ch. 2]. Each thread runs independently and may execute a different instruction at any given time, making TLP especially useful for general-purpose applications and irregular workloads. TLP is supported via software frameworks such as OpenMP [35] for shared-memory systems and MPI [36] for distributed systems. Multi-core architectures in the early 2000s, notably with IBM's POWER4 in 2001, marked the start of widespread adoption of TLP at the hardware level [27]. Accelerators such as GPUs introduce a compressed form of thread level parallelism with the SIMT (Single instruction multiple threads) paradigm. SIMT spreads concurrent workloads across multiple threads [15, Sec. 7.1]. While SIMT (Single Instruction, Multiple Threads) is fundamentally a form of thread-level parallelism, it organizes threads into small groups called *warps*, which typically execute the same instruction in parallel across multiple threads. This warp-level execution makes SIMT appear similar to data-level parallelism, particularly in regular workloads where threads follow the same control flow. Although each thread maintains its own execution context, the hardware schedules and dispatches instructions at the warp granularity, making SIMT especially effective for exploiting massive data-parallel workloads.

Task-level parallelism and MPI

Task-level parallelism refers to the concurrent execution of multiple independent tasks, each of which may represent a distinct computational operation or a separate part of a larger workflow [31, ch. 2]. A task can involve running its own instruction stream, managing data independently, and potentially introducing thread-level parallelism within its local execution context. Task-level parallelism can involve decomposing a problem domain and evenly distributing work between multiple nodes in a data center [21, p. 368]. Communication between these nodes is typically handled using the Message Passing Interface (MPI) [36, Ch. 1], where each task is assigned to a separate process—often on different machines or GPUs. These tasks operate independently and coordinate through explicit message passing, enabling scalable parallel execution of large workloads.

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2.2 Microprocessor

x86 Architecture

In this section, the architecture of a modern microprocessor will be examined using an example: the AMD EPYC 9334 processor. This system was released in Q4 2022 [37] and featured the Zen 4 core architecture [38]. Although the processor and the underlying architecture do not represent the most recent of AMDs products (as the Zen 5 architecture has been released in Q4 2024 [37]), we used this specific system for the experimental results where a microprocessor was the subject of investigation 5, hence the AMD EPYCTM 9334 system was selected to provide a case study on x86 architectures.

The general structure of the core design features the division into a front-end, back-end, and the memory subsystem, which includes caching and off-core data transfers. An overview of the architectural core design (Zen 4) is provided in Figure Figure 2.3. The front end includes the instruction fetch and instruction decode phase of the pipeline Section 2.1. Instructions are fetched from global memory (initially) into a fast 32 KiB L1 instruction cache, which resides on the core-die. During the decode phase, complex x86-instructions from the instruction cache are reduced to multiple micro-operations. On the Zen 4 architecture, four instructions can be decoded concurrently per cycle. Note that this part of the front end only has to perform decoding instructions that were absent in the micro-op cache, which acts as a shortcut for already decoded instructions. A front-end is usually aided by a deep branch prediction unit, allowing it to decode predictably selected branches far ahead of the conditional check. (e.g Boolean compare operation) This unit is a main characteristic of the multiprocessor back-end as it allows high throughput in serial instruction streams with advanced branching logic, whereas an accelerator relies on deterministic execution patterns, often minimizing or avoiding complex branching logic. After an instruction has been successfully decoded by the front-end, it is stored in a *micro-op queue* also referred to as *dispatch queue*. From this queue, micro-operations are dispatched in-order to the rename stage, where register definitions from the ISA (instruction set architecture) are translated to physical registers. This allows eliminating false dependencies (e.g read after write) [21, page 196] and indirectly reduce register pressure. The reorder buffer (ROB) receives renamed instructions in-order and tracks their completion

Figure 2.3: Zen 4 core architecture overview and memory subsystem (based on data from [38] and [39])

status. After instructions are registered in the reorder buffer, the out-of-order section of the pipeline begins. Operations are dispatched to various scheduling queues depending on their instruction type. A wide back-end that holds various execution units for floating point and integer operations can execute instructions in parallel by leveraging resource efficient *out-of-order* scheduling (handled by scheduling queues) and concurrently processing execution unit (such as multiple AGU, ALU). A memory access (store/load) involves the calculation of the effective address in an AGU unit, which subsequently gets stored in the load/store queue to allow fine-grained scheduling of memory instructions. In the mean time the virtual address is translated into a physical addresses through L1 DTLB (data table lookup buffer), if there is no entry for the virtual address found in the L1 DTLB (72 entries), the request is transferred to the larger L2 DTLB (3072 entries). L2 DTLB misses are handled by accompanying hardware page table walkers.

When issuing load/store requests to physical addresses, the modern microprocessor supports multi-level caching, where lower cache level (regarding the number - LX) allow for a higher bandwidth and lower latency as they are closer to the core. The increased bandwidth and lower latency come at the cost of a reduced capacity. Since not every instruction/data can be stored in the L1 caches they are evicted into higher level caches, where subsequent requests would result in a latency that is higher than the closest L1-cache yet still significantly lower than a request to global memory. The L1 and L2 levels of the Zen4 architectures are exclusive to each core, whereas the L3-Cache is shared within a core complex, further the L1 Cache is divided into spatially distributed partitions handling instructions and Data separately. Similar design choices for the memory subsystems can be found in contemporary Intel processors, such as those based on the Alder Lake or Raptor Lake microarchitectures. Since fetching instructions from higher level caches can involve 10x the amount of instruction cycles, effective resource utilization is critical, therefore various prefetchers are employed in the Zen 4 architecture which perform memory requests based on a memory access pattern ahead of time. These include three L1- and two L2 prefetchers for next line, stride and more complex but consistent patterns (for a detailed differentiation between various prefetchers refer to [38, page 41]). While the architecture of an individual core is a critical aspect in architectural design, the uncore area of modern CPUs—comprising shared resources such as L3

Figure 2.4: Core complex die (CCD) - configuration using eight cores contained in AMD EPYC 9334 (based on [37])

Figure 2.5: I/O Die configuration on AMD EPYC 9334 and example dual socket interconnect using 4x16 PCIe 5.0 lanes (based on [37])

cache, memory controllers, and interconnect fabrics, significantly contributes to the energy consumption [40] as well as bandwidth and latency. In a modern microprocessor, individual cores communicate via shared memory, which introduces significant latency if data must be retrieved from another core's private cache or from DRAM. This is where the L3 cache plays a critical role it introduces a low-latency, shared buffer for inter-core communication. It allows cores to efficiently share data without the full cost of main memory access. AMD adopts a modular approach in its EPYC architecture, grouping cores into Core Complex Dies (CCDs). A Core Complex Die (CCD), which consists of up to 16 cores [37] and an L3 cache (acting as the shared memory interconnect between cores within a CCD). Figure 2.4 is depicting a configuration consisting of eight cores and a 32 MiB interconnect. Communication between CCDs, as well as between CCDs and the I/O Die, is facilitated by AMD's Infinity Fabric—a scalable interconnect that links all elements of the processor package. The I/O Die serves as the central communication hub, managing cache coherence across CCDs via a directory-based protocol, ensuring consistency and synchronization of shared memory operations across the entire socket. Up to 12 CCDs are connected to the I/O-Die via GMI ports. Since the EPYC 9334 configuration only contains four CCDs, each CCD can utilize two of those GMI ports, effectively doubling the bandwidth. The I/O Die also contains a twelve unified memory controller (UMC) that manages communication over DDR-5 memory channels. In addition to the I/O Die, Figure 2.5 also illustrates the inter-socket connection enabled by AMD's xGMI links. Each socket provides 128 PCIe Gen 5 lanes, of which up to 64 lanes can be repurposed for inter-socket

communication via xGMI, depending on the platform configuration.

Various architectural design philosophies exist for the memory and data transfer interconnect on modern server microprocessors, with AMD adopting a modular approach by grouping cores into Core Complex Dies (CCDs), whereas Intel utilizes a mesh-based topology [41, fig. 5] to interconnect cores through a distributed L3 cache. While there are various architectural design philosophies, AMD has adopted a modular approach by grouping cores into Core Complex Dies (CCDs), whereas Intel utilizes a mesh-based topology to interconnect cores through a distributed L3 cache. Despite these differences, a unifying architectural element is the use of a local L3 cache as a foundational interconnect mechanism across cores. The discussion here does not aim to exhaustively cover all microarchitectural details, but rather with the example of the AMD EPYC 9334 to provide the reader with a foundational understanding of multiprocessor host architectures, which is essential given the host's central role in orchestrating accelerated computing (CPU-GPU) workflows and its relevance as a potential back-end target for alpaka 3.

OpenMP Programming Model

OpenMP (Open Multiprocessing) [42] was first developed for fortran in 1997 and was released in C++ in 1998. Since then, it continued to develop into the quasi-standard for shared-memory parallel programming widely supported by modern tool-chains such as GCC, LLVM/Clang, and Intel oneAPI. Its core model is based on multi-threading through compiler directives, allowing the developer to annotate C++ code for parallel execution across threads, tasks, and, more recently, target devices. Typically, OpenMP utilizes POSIX threads (pthreads) to enable thread-level parallelism (TLP). This allows programs to execute concurrently across multiple physical cores, particularly on multiprocessor systems. Recent OpenMP versions show support for GPU-offloading, allowing programmers to run C++ programs on a GPU without the need to adapt a vendor-specific API. GPU offloading is especially beneficial in heterogeneous environment hosting multiple GPUs from different vendors. But, while these are noticeable similarities to the goals of alpaka 3, they differ significantly in the level of abstraction and control granularity. OpenMP enables communication through shared memory, where threads can access a common address space. Race conditions for common resources can be mitigated by synchronization through `#pragma omp barrier` or `#pragma omp critical` sections [43].

In the context of this work OpenMP is important, as it can be utilized as a potential Back-end for alpaka 3 [11] and therefore critical resources such as the number of threads spawned by OpenMP it becomes a tuning parameter in the hereby proposed tuning framework. OpenMP provides several environment variables to control thread placement and binding:

- `OMP_PROC_BIND` — discourages thread migration by setting thread affinity,
- `OMP_PLACES` — defines the logical mapping of threads to processing units.

These can be set in order to ensure that threads remain on fixed, nearby cores throughout execution, thereby enhancing data locality and reducing performance variability caused by thread migration or suboptimal placement.

2.3 NVIDIA

The upcoming section will use the NVIDIA Hopper GH100 architecture to examine the design of modern GPU-based accelerators. The product SKU H100-SXM5 will be used in the experimental evaluation presented later in this work 5. While H100-SXM5 denotes a specific hardware configuration and packaging format, the underlying manufactured GPU die is codenamed GH100. To remain consistent, we will refer to the design as GH100 throughout the following architectural discussion.

Nvidia Architecture

The modern nvidia accelerator is composed of several processing units called streaming multiprocessor (SM). A SM shares characteristics with the core on a multiprocessor, as it has its own instruction cache and scheduling unit(s). Each SM contains multiple warp schedulers, which manage the execution of **warps** — groups of 32 threads that execute in lockstep [15, sec. 5.2]. A H100 GPU SM hosts four compartments or processing blocks. Each of these partitions includes its own L0 instruction cache, warp scheduler, registers and instruction dispatch unit enabling the SM to issue and manage up to four warps per clock cycle concurrently [44, p. 21].

Each SM also supports instruction-level parallelism (ILP) by distributing independent instructions from separate warps to different execution units [15, ch. 8]. This allows SM to sustain high throughput under mixed workloads. The load/store units within a processing block are optimized for coalesced memory accesses, enabling memory transactions from multiple threads in a warp to be combined into a smaller number of global memory requests when access patterns are aligned. Coalesced memory access occurs when the memory addresses accessed by all threads in a warp are located within a contiguous and properly aligned segment of memory. This allows 32 bit memory operations to be combined into 128 bit memory operations [15, sec. 8.3, p. 167]. Shared memory, tensor memory accelerator and L1

A **processing block** also contains several execution and memory units, as depicted in Figure 2.6. These include:

- 16 × FP64 execution units (64 per SM)
- 32 × FP32 execution units (128 per SM)
- 16 × INT32 or mixed-precision FP32/INT units (64 per SM)
- 8 × Load/Store (LD/ST) units (32 per SM)
- 1 × Special Function Unit (SFU) (4 per SM)
- 1 × Tensor Core (4th generation) (4 per SM)

Figure 2.6: Streaming Multiprocessor from a GH100 (from [44])

Figure 2.7: Full GH100 Compute die (from [44])

instruction cache are collaboratively accessed by all processing blocks, allowing threads from different warps, scheduled across partitions, to collaboratively access shared data structures with low latency [44, pp. 21–22].

Moving to the Top-Level Architecture design of the GH100 GPU, which is depicted in Figure 2.7, we can see that 18 SMs are composed of a GPU Processing Clusters (GPC). While GPCs did not traditionally have any meaning from a programming standpoint, the Hopper architecture allows to implement localized distributed shared memory accesses between SMs that are co-located within the same GPC group [44, p. 22], supported in CUDA as *thread block clusters* [15, sec. 5.2.1]. In total, the **144 streaming multiprocessors** are potentially available on the GH100 die, although most of the SDKs.

The 50 MiB L2 cache is physically partitioned into two memory slices, as shown in Figure 2.7 and was further confirmed by Luo et al. [45, sec. 3; sec. 4.1], who performed fine-grained pointer tracking micro-benchmarks and identified two distinct latency groups for L2 accesses, corresponding to near and far partitions relative to accessing SM [45, sec. 4.1]. Each L2 slice is connected not only to local SMs, but interfaces with the external DRAM via an HBM memory controller. These controllers are responsible for transferring data between the L2 cache hierarchy and the GPU’s main memory. Memory requests that miss in L2 are routed to the appropriate partition controller (assigned to a certain partition of the L2 cache), which issues the request to the corresponding HBM stack.

From the GPU’s perspective, external memory is organized using **High Bandwidth Memory (HBM)**, a 3D-stacked DRAM technology that is integrated directly onto the GPU package. Extremely wide interfaces (typically 1024 bits per stack) allow HBM memory throughput to significantly outperform DDR memory. In our setup - on the *Capella* [46] cluster - we utilize an H100 variant equipped with 94 GB of **HBM2e** memory, this H100 SXM5 production variant hosts **132** out of the 144 streaming multiprocessors (SM) incorporated on the GH100 die.

For host-device communication, the GH100 supports two types of external interfaces: *PCIe Gen5* and *NVLink 4.0* [44, p. 13]. Later can be used to enable high bandwidth communication between GPUs.

CUDA Programming Model

The following section should provide the reader with a brief overview of the most commonly used software back-ends to program NVIDIA GPUs, more comprehensive information is found in the CUDA programming guide [15]. The CUDA programming model was first introduced in 2006 as a general purpose parallel computing model that leverages the NVIDIA computing engine, and therefore only supports NVIDIA GPUs. Compared to other programming models such as OpenMP with target offloading,

Figure 2.8: Parallel processing hierarchy of the CUDA programming model (based on [15, sec. 5.2])

CUDA enables higher performance in many cases by exposing a syntax and execution model, that remains closer to the underlying hardware resources. In addition to its own syntax and compilers CUDA also introduces certain concepts which are necessary to program in that language. CUDA imposes a redundant parallel hierarchy, which is depicted in Figure 2.8. Another concept introduced by CUDA is *shared memory*, which maps to a low-latency memory partition local to each Streaming Multiprocessor (SM). Shared memory enables efficient intra-block communication and is often used for data reuse (such as stencil code or matrix multiplication), reduction operations, and avoiding costly global memory

Table 2.1: Mapping between CUDA’s redundant hierarchy software abstractions and NVIDIA GPU hardware components.

Software Abstraction	Hardware Counterpart	Description
Thread	Thread	Smallest execution unit, has its own registers and program counter. Since the NVIDIA Volta architecture divergent branches may be executed asynchronously within a warp - warps may also diverge when issuing memory instructions [47, sec. 1.4.1.2].
Warp	Warp (32 threads)	A group of 32 threads executed together and managed by the warp scheduler. Although warp level synchronization and intra warp operations via intrinsics are supported by CUDA, the concept of a warp is not a native part of the CUDA parallel hierarchy model (as visualized in Figure 2.8) [15, sec. 5.2].
thread-block	Streaming Multiprocessor (SM)	A group of threads organized in 1D/2D/3D that all execute on the same SM. Threads within a block can cooperate using shared memory and synchronize execution. CUDA also imposes restrictions on the number of resident threads per thread-block. These limits are architecture-specific and can be queried at runtime via the CUDA API (e.g., <code>cudaDeviceGetAttribute</code>). For example, the NVIDIA GH100 architecture supports up to 2048 resident threads per block [15, sec. 20.6.2].
grid	Collection of SMs	Represents the complete kernel launch. It contains multiple thread-blocks scheduled across all available SMs, the grid is also described in 1D/2D/3D similar to the thread-block. Blocks in a grid cannot communicate directly via shared memory [15, sec. 5.2].

accesses [15, sec. 5.3]. To complement the informations provided in Section 2.3 recent CUDA versions (>12.0) also feature a intermediate layer between thread-blocks and Grid called Thread-block cluster. A thread-block cluster is executed on one GPU Processing Clusters and enables the usage of distributed shared memory [15, sec. 5.2.1].

2.4 AMD

AMD Architecture

Since the architectural design of a modern GPU was discussed in Section 2.3, we now focus on fundamental differences in AMD’s design philosophy compared to NVIDIA’s GH100 (Hopper). While NVIDIA GPUs are structured around SMs and warps (groups of 32 threads), AMD GPUs use Compute Units (CUs) and *wavefronts*, typically consisting of 64 threads [48]. A wavefront is AMD’s functional equivalent of a warp, executing instructions in SIMD fashion, with all threads in a wavefront locked to a single instruction stream—similar to NVIDIA architectures preceding Volta [47, sec. 1.4.1.2].

The AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX [48, 49] is a consumer graphics card based on the RDNA 3 architecture and GFX1100 ISA. It is used as our AMD GPU test device in Chapter 5. The system employs a chiplet design (rather than a monolithic die). RDNA 3 features six Memory Cache Dies providing a total of 96 MiB of L3 cache alongside a central Graphics Compute Die. The GPU features 96 CUs, organized into 48 Dual Compute Units (DCUs), with each DCU housing two SIMD32 execution units; a full wavefront of 64 threads executes over two cycles by these SIMD units. The RX 7900 XTX is equipped with 24 GiB of GDDR6 memory [49].

HIP Programming Model

HIP [16] (Heterogeneous-computing Interface for Portability) is AMD’s GPU programming model that enables developers to write portable, high-performance code for AMD and NVIDIA GPUs. HIP closely mirrors the CUDA programming interface, exposing familiar abstractions such as `threadIdx`, `blockIdx`, and CUDA-style kernel launch syntax [16]. HIP is tightly integrated with AMD’s ROCm platform [48], which provides the runtime, compiler infrastructure, and low-level driver support; when targeting AMD hardware, HIP compiles device code via LLVM-based back ends using the ROCm toolchain [16].

2.5 alpaka – A Heterogeneous Programming Library

The original alpaka library [10] was developed in 2016 by Zenker et. al., with the goal of providing a performance-portable programming interface for heterogeneous architectures. alpaka achieves this by abstracting hardware-specific parallelism into a unified model, enabling a single-source programming style that can target multiple execution platforms. Initially designed to support NVIDIA GPUs through a CUDA back-end, subsequent developments extended alpaka’s back-end support to include AMD GPUs via HIP and Intel architectures (including GPUs) via SYCL.

In particular, with the general SYCL back-end, alpaka can target not only CPUs and GPUs, but also FPGAs or any architecture supported by Intel’s oneAPI compilers. The heterogeneous programming capabilities of alpaka are further amplified by its CPU back-end for parallel execution (supported by OpenMP), which allow the same codebase to be compiled and executed for both host CPU’s and accelerators.

Even without the aid of a dedicated tuning mechanism, alpaka has demonstrated strong code portability and performance scalability across different compute architectures [13].

The tuning framework presented in this thesis has been integrated into the successor of the original alpaka library [10]. This successor, referred to as alpaka 3, was in the prototyping stage during the time this thesis was carried out. Before we examine the alpaka 3’s programming model, we first have to lay down

fundamental concepts and terminologies. While most of the key concepts are already explained in the original publication [10] and remained mostly the same in the succeeding alpaka 3 version, we will briefly denote some of these ideas, which will be used throughout the remainder of this thesis. Additionally there are noticeable differences in the alpaka versions as the successor alpaka 3 not only simplifies the user interface by adopting object-oriented abstractions, but also introduces a novel concept for providing problem description which allows simple adaption to underlying architectures with different resource hierarchies and compute capabilities. This concept, termed *Frame Specification*, will be discussed in detail in Section 2.5. Its adaptability to the aforementioned back-ends will be analyzed subsequently. For clarity, unless explicitly referring to the legacy version of alpaka, the term "alpaka" will henceforth denote the prototype version, alpaka 3.

Terminology: Kernel

An *alpaka kernel* is, in the words of the original authors [13] “the central unit in alpaka that acts as the bridge between host and accelerator code”. A basic kernel must implement the a functor `operator()`, which takes the accelerator `acc` as the primary argument and user defined function arguments (such as `buffer`):

Listing 2.1: A skeleton of an ALPAKA kernel

```
struct Kernel {
    template<typename TAcc>
    ALPAKA_FN_ACC void operator() (TAcc const& acc, auto buffer, ...,
        uint32_t argN) const {
        // Device code
    }
};
```

The `ALPAKA_FN_ACC` macro marks the function as executable on the accelerator. Additional macros such as `ALPAKA_FN_HOST` or `ALPAKA_FN_HOST_ACC` enable hybrid execution across host and device [10].

From a practical and intuitive point of view, a alpaka kernel can be understood as a computational unit that encapsulates a part of the device-side logic of the program. Conceptually, it is similar to a CUDA or HIP kernel in that its body expresses the problem logic meant to run on the selected device. However, unlike CUDA kernels, alpaka kernels are back-end-agnostic. They are not limited to GPUs, and can be compiled and executed on a variety of devices as described previously.

In this sense, the alpaka kernel serves as a portable envelope of compute logic, capable of being dispatched to any back-end supported by the alpaka runtime. Once a back-end is selected and a device context is established, the kernel is instantiated and can be executed there - without modification to the kernel code itself. To pass arguments to the kernel during execution, the kernel functor can be wrapped in a `KernelBundle`, which forwards those arguments to the `operator()` function when the kernel is launched.

Queue

An alpaka queue stores and dispatches tasks (such as memory transfers or kernel executions) in a sequential order on one device, while executing asynchronously with respect to the host-side program. Multiple alpaka queues can be used to emulate behavior similar to multiple CUDA streams, enabling concurrent execution and finer control over kernel scheduling. Device to host synchronization is achieved by calling `wait()` on a queue.

Programming Model - Frame Specification

In the following section, we will explore how alpaka allows a general description of a problem under varying execution environments and resource constraints. More specifically we will discuss how established quantities such as number of thread-blocks and the number of threads can be adapted without violating the correctness of the program.

Similar concepts are found in contemporary abstraction libraries such as Kokkos [9], which uses *execution spaces*, *memory spaces*, and hierarchical *execution policies* to abstract over back-end-specific resources and execution hierarchies. First, we have to lay down more concepts and terminology used in alpaka, starting with the frame specification, which consists of three key parameters:

- Number of frames (`numFrames`)
- Number of frame elements in a Frame (`frameExtent`)
- Thread specification (`ThreadSpec`)

The frame specification is used to decompose a problem in a two-level hierarchy, similar to CUDA. It is passed to the queue alongside the Kernel object, in order to be accessible during Kernel execution. A notable feature of alpaka is that all vectors, which are used to describe buffer extents, and parameters of the frame specifications, or thread specifications—can be n -dimensional. This generalization goes beyond CUDA’s restriction to at most three dimensions.

The small example provided in Listing 1 demonstrates how a user would typically provide a frame specification for a one-dimensional input data buffer containing 4096 elements, such that the number sum of all frame elements is equal to the number of data elements in the buffer. Notice that the `ThreadSpec` that was mentioned before as the third parameter of the frame specification does not appear in the code snippet provided.

```
// Include the necessary namespace
using namespace alpaka;
// create alpaka::queue on the device
auto queue = ...
// example problem size using 1-dimensional alpaka vector
auto arraySize = Vector{4096};
// initializing host buffer
auto bufHost = onHost::allocHost<float>(arraySize);
// initializing accelerator buffer (same size as host buffer)
auto bufAcc = allocMirror(bufHost);

// get the extent from host buffer
auto arrayExtent = bufHost.getExtents();
auto frameExtent = Vector{512};
// define the extent of each frame
auto numFrames = divCeil(arraySize, frameExtent);
// compute number of frames
auto spec = FrameSpec{numFrames, frameExtent};
// initialize frame spec
auto bufSpan = bufAcc.getMdSpan();
queue.enqueue(executor, spec, KernelBundle{TestKernel{}}, bufSpan);
// launch kernel
```

Listing 1: A small example demonstrating the decomposition of a one-dimensional array—used as our example problem domain—using the frame specification and launching a kernel in alpaka 3

Table 2.2: Mapping of parameters defined by alpaka’s ThreadSpec to hardware related resources on several execution backends.

	CUDA	HIP	SYCL	OpenMP
<code>numThreads</code> or <code>threads</code>	Threads per thread-block. Executed in warps on Nvidia GPU’s.	Threads per thread-block or HIP-block. Executed in wavefronts on AMD GPUs.	Work-items per work-group.	Set to a univector.
<code>numBlocks</code> or <code>thread-block’s</code>	Number of thread-blocks in the grid.	Grid of HIP blocks. Scheduled on compute units on AMD GPUs.	Work-groups in the SYCL ND-range.	Defines a number of loop iterations (<code>#omp parallel for</code>), each potentially executed by a separate thread from the available <code>OMP_NUM_THREADS</code> .

That is because the thread specification (ThreadSpec), which consists of the number of:

- Number of thread-blocks (`numBlocks`)
- Number of threads (`numThreads`)

In contrast to the `FrameSpec`, the `ThreadSpec` is not necessarily tied to the index space or domain decomposition. Instead, it targets back-end-specific hardware resources and determines the number of active workers involved during kernel execution. As such, alpaka typically selects a reasonable configuration automatically. However, users can override this behavior and specify the `ThreadSpec` directly, potentially leading to reduced portability.

In Listing 1, the `ThreadSpec` is configured by the default constructor of the `FrameSpec` with `numBlocks = numFrames` and `numThreads = frameExtent`.

Note that when running on the OpenMP back-end, alpaka might not support thread-level decomposition. Consequently, alpaka internally modifies the parameter `numThreads` by assigning it to a univector.

Since `ThreadSpec` is loosely defined and closely related to hardware characteristics, Table 2.2 provides an overview of how the parameters `numBlocks` and `numThreads` map to back-end-specific hardware resources.

Throughout this thesis, the terms `thread-blocks` and `threads` are used in accordance with the CUDA terminology to denote the elements defined by the thread specification. This consistent use applies across all back-ends and aligns with the abstraction provided by alpaka 3.

A central motivation for employing a two-level decomposition in parallel programming lies in the separation of responsibilities between the thread- and block levels. At the thread level, computations are typically fine-grained and data-parallel, with each thread operating independently on a portion of the data. The block level, on the other hand, introduces coordination among threads within the same block and facilitates access to shared resources.

alpaka 3 supports these block-level mechanisms through high-level abstractions. Shared memory, for instance, can be allocated either statically or dynamically and is scoped per thread-block. This enables fast communication between threads within the same block and promotes data reuse. Additionally, alpaka

provides block-level synchronization primitives that enforce barrier semantics: All threads within a block must reach a synchronization point before any of them can proceed. This mechanism ensures correct coordination in algorithms that rely on intermediate results being available across multiple threads in a block. Table 2.3 summarizes the block-level synchronization and shared memory mechanisms provided by specific back-end APIs, which alpaka unifies under common abstractions.

Iterators and index mapping

To abstract away the number of available workers (i.e., threads and thread-blocks) from the index space, alpaka provides a mapping utility function called `makeIdxMap`. The following code snippet is intended to be used within a kernel and defines the range of values over which a specified execution group (e.g., threads in a block or grid) iterates:

```
for (auto idx : onAcc::makeIdxMap(acc, group, IdxRange{start, end,
    stride}, T_layout, T_traverse))
```

Each element in the group retrieves a *unique set of indices* from the specified range `[start, end)` using the given `stride`, ensuring no overlap between workers. This range defines the *local index space* — the set of indices over which the execution group operates.

The function returns a range-based iterator that maps a portion of the index space to the calling worker. This mapping behavior is controlled by two types of policy: the `layout` policy (`T_layout`) and the `traverse` policy (`T_traverse`). Figure 2.9 provides a visual illustration of how different combinations of mapping policies affect the index-space assigned to individual workers.

Table 2.3: Back-end realization of alpaka’s portable synchronization and shared memory model.

Back-end	Block-Level Synchronization	Shared Memory Support
CUDA	<code>__syncthreads()</code> Available for synchronizing threads within a thread-block.	<code>__shared__</code> memory (static and dynamic) is explicitly defined and backed by fast on-chip memory.
HIP	<code>__syncthreads()</code> Identical semantics to CUDA. Used for thread-block level barriers.	<code>__shared__</code> memory is supported on AMD GPUs. Usage mirrors CUDA.
SYCL (oneAPI)	<code>group_barrier()</code> Used for synchronizing work-items within a work-group.	<code>local_accessor</code> provides shared memory, but its backing (on-chip vs. global) is hardware- and compiler-dependent.
OpenMP	one thread per thread-block -> serial execution on block level	Uses stack allocated memory to emulate shared memory (limited size to prevent overflow).

Table 2.4: Comparison of Layout and Traversal Policies

Policy Type	Variant	Mapping Style
Layout	<code>layout::contiguous</code>	Index-space is divided into contiguous chunks; each worker gets a continuous block of indices.
	<code>layout::strided</code>	Index-space is distributed in a round-robin (interleaved) fashion. Each worker gets indices spaced by the number of workers.
Traverse	<code>traverse::flat</code>	The index-space is flattened to a one-dimensional list.
	<code>traverse::tiled</code>	Preserves the multi-dimensional structure of the index-space. Workers operate on n-dimensional tiles rather than flat index ranges.

Figure 2.9: Visual representation of alpaka's mapping policies based on an example using a mapping from a 2x2 worker group (e.g. numThreads) to a 4x4 index-space (e.g. arraySize). Colors represent individual workers. White letters denote the 0-indexed loop iteration, for each worker respectively.

When not explicitly specified, alpaka selects default values for the layout and traversal policies for every index mapping depending on the execution back-end.

On CPU back-ends, the default is `layout::contiguous` combined with `traverse::flat`: each worker is assigned a sequential block of indices. This access pattern aligns with the cache-line based memory load granularity of CPUs (typically 64 bytes), reducing the number of load operations when accessing consecutive elements. Contiguous assignments also help avoid false sharing between threads by keeping memory accesses within non-overlapping cache-lines. Additionally, regular, linear access patterns are more likely to trigger hardware prefetchers (e.g. next-line prefetcher) and might encourage compiler auto-vectorization.

On GPU back-ends, the Default is `layout::strided` with `traverse::tiled`: each thread receives indices spaced by the total number of threads in the group. When those indices are used to read a linear array, adjacent threads in a warp reference consecutive words, allowing the hardware to coalesce their requests into wide 32-, 64-, or 128-byte memory transactions. Even if individual loads are not merged, the requested data still reside in the same cache line, increasing L2 hit rates. Because every

thread in a warp incurs similar latency, intra-warp divergence is also reduced. These defaults are selected to encourage performance-friendly index mappings, but achieving optimal memory behavior ultimately depends on the kernel logic and data layout chosen by the programmer.

Kernel Description Based on the Frame Specification

This section combines the previously introduced frame specification with alpaka’s `makeIdxMap` utility to construct a two-level loop structure. The decomposition maps logical frames to thread-blocks and frame elements to individual threads, providing a resource-agnostic abstraction of the problem.

Although the kernel in Listing 2.2 could be simplified to a single loop mapping all threads directly to `arrayExtent`, the structure shown here explicitly leverages the hierarchical execution model of alpaka:

- **Outer loop (blocks → frames):** assigns complete frames to thread-blocks, enabling block-local reuse, shared memory staging or synchronization.
- **Middle loop (threads → elements):** maps threads to elements within each frame, defining per-

Listing 2.2: Hardware resource-agnostic kernel description based on the frame specification

```

struct Kernel
{
    template<typename TAcc>
    ALPAKA_FN_ACC auto operator() (
        TAcc const& acc,
        alpaka::concepts::Vector auto arrayExtent,
        alpaka::concepts::MdSpan auto arrayView) {
        auto numFrames = acc[frame::count];
        auto frameExtent = acc[frame::extent];
        auto frameDomain = numFrames * frameExtent;
        using IndexType = decltype(frameExtent)::type;
        auto zeroVector = Vector<>::all(0);
        // define a strided loop over the frameDomain
        // where thread-blocks are mapped to frames
        for (auto frameStartIdx : onAcc::makeIdxMap(
            acc,
            onAcc::worker::blocksInGrid,
            IdxRange{zeroVector, frameDomain, frameExtent}))
        {
            // on this level we can leverage block-level synchronisation for example
            alpaka::onAcc::syncBlockThreads(acc);
            // define a mapping of threads to frameElements.
            // each thread might handle multiple frame Elements ->
            // potentially increasing ILP
            for (auto elementInFrameIdx : onAcc::makeIdxMap( // threads to elements
                acc,
                onAcc::worker::threadsInBlock,
                IdxRange{frameExtent}))
            {
                auto frameElementIndex = frameStartIdx + elementInFrameIdx;
                // we define a mapping of the index space to the data space
                for (auto dataIdx : onAcc::makeIdxMap(
                    acc,
                    onAcc::WorkerGroup{frameElementIndex},
                    IdxRange{arrayExtent}))
                {
                    auto element = arrayView[dataIdx];
                    ...
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

thread workloads -> potentially increasing ILP as each thread handles multiple elements.

- **Inner loop (index mapping):** maps frame-local indices to global data indices. This loop is only necessary if `arrayExtent mod frameExtent \neq zeroVector`; otherwise, the global index can be directly computed as `frameStartIdx + elementInFrameIdx`, and used to index `arrayView` without further indirection, in general this is only true provided the `FrameSpec` is defined as shown in Listing 1.

This layered mapping increases flexibility: it supports frame-wise tiling, shared-memory reuse, and chunked execution across devices with varying hardware constraints—without altering kernel logic. It also permits reconfiguring the number of thread-blocks and threads between kernel launches without affecting the correctness of the result.

SIMD and Instruction-Level Parallelism in alpaka

To enhance data locality and parallelism within a single worker, alpaka provides an explicit `SIMD::Algo` abstraction. From the perspective of the programming model, this means that one logical worker (e.g., defined by a frame specification) operates not on a single data element, but on one or more fixed-width groups of elements, where each element group is represented by a `SIMD` object. This means `SIMD::Algo` allows individual workers to perform collective operations over such packs. Furthermore it provides an interface that allows users to provide descriptions following SIMD operations. The `SIMD::Algo` essentially consists of two stages: The first introduces `SIMD` objects and determines their size and the second one uses Instruction level parallelism by defining how many consecutive `SIMD` objects are handled by one worker.

An alpaka `SIMD` object encapsulates a compile-time-sized, memory-aligned pack of values and supports standard arithmetic and logical operators. These operators are implemented as element-wise loops over the values in the pack. The use of `alignas` ensures that memory accesses to the pack are naturally aligned, enabling back-end-specific optimizations: on CPUs, compilers are more likely to emit efficient vector instructions via auto-vectorization; on GPUs, aligned and consecutive loads by neighboring threads can be merged into wide, coalesced memory transactions.

A similar low-overhead abstraction, `std::simd`, is expected to become part of the C++ Standard Library in C++26.

alpaka determines the SIMD width based on back-end-specific architectural constraints.

- On **CPU back-ends**, the pack width is chosen to match the size of a native vector register (e.g., SSE, AVX2, AVX-512). This alignment increases the likelihood of auto-vectorization by the compiler. The aligned pack is typically sized to fit within a cache line, minimizing false sharing and promoting spatial locality.
- On **GPU back-ends**, the pack width is generally set to the maximum per-thread vector load (often 16 bytes), in alignment with hardware capabilities for coalesced memory accesses. Proper alignment allows hardware to merge loads across threads into wide memory transactions, reducing memory latency and improving bandwidth utilization.

In the second stage alpaka determines how many consecutive SIMD packs a single worker should process. The library computes the number of packs that can be handled efficiently by one worker. On CPUs, the number of packs takes into account the cache-line size and aims to avoid false sharing by aligning the total memory footprint of a worker's data, as well as the number of available vector execution units. On GPUs, it reflects the number of scheduler slots (NVIDIA) or vector execution units (AMD, Intel) available per thread. From an architectural perspective, increasing the number of independent operations within a thread enables the compiler or hardware to schedule multiple instructions simultaneously or in rapid succession, reducing pipeline stalls and improving utilization of execution units. On CPUs,

this helps saturate multiple vector execution pipelines and hide instruction latencies by issuing independent arithmetic or memory operations back-to-back. On GPUs, where threads may be stalled due to memory latency or control divergence, computing multiple SIMD packs per thread increases the number of independent instructions available for scheduling. This improves instruction throughput and helps the hardware better utilize its execution resources across diverse architectures, thereby improving throughput and latency hiding [50].

This two-stage design—first selecting an appropriate SIMD pack size, then determining how many such packs to assign per worker—enables alpaka to balance memory alignment, throughput, and ILP in a back-end-specific manner. The user can also override the default settings, explicitly controlling the number of concurrent bytes processed by one worker via `Simd`, making the `concurrencyInBytes` a suitable candidate for autotuning.

2.6 Problem Description – Formal Definition of Autotuning

Autotuning is defined as the automatic process of optimizing application performance by iteratively modifying configurable parameters in search of the best-performing configuration. Autotuning refers to the automatic process of optimizing application performance by iteratively adjusting configurable parameters in search of the best-performing configuration. Pfeffe et al. [51] introduce a formalism for describing autotuning, which we adopt and present below. The central component of this formalism is a *measurement function*

$$m_K : T \rightarrow \mathbb{R},$$

where:

- T is the *tuning space*, composed of all parameter configurations.
- $K = (K_A, K_S)$ is the *context*, representing the application A and the system S it runs on.
- The optimization target is defined as:

$$C_{\text{opt},K} = \arg \min_{C \in T} m_K(C),$$

which denotes the configuration C that minimizes m_K , i.e., yields the best performance under context K .

The tuning space T is defined as the Cartesian product of tuning parameters:

$$T = \tau_0 \times \tau_1 \times \cdots \times \tau_J,$$

where each τ_j represents the domain of the j -th tuning parameter. Moreover, we define *tuning parameters* as parameters whose values do not affect *functional correctness* of the algorithm. That is, all configurations in the tuning space T yield semantically valid output. However, tuning parameters may influence *non-functional properties* such as numerical precision. Additionally, we will later introduce additional constraints on the valid configurations such that T will only be a subset of the Cartesian product, but for the sake of simplicity this is not relevant for the current discussion.

2.7 Strategy

Problem description - Formal definition

Autotuning is defined as the automatic process of optimizing application performance by iteratively modifying configurable parameters in search of the best-performing configuration. Autotuning refers to the automatic process of optimizing application performance by iteratively adjusting configurable

parameters in search of the best-performing configuration. Pfeffe et al. [51] introduce a formalism for describing autotuning, which we adopt and present below. The central component of this formalism is a *measurement function*

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Exhaustive Search

This contains all the methods that cover all possible parameter configurations. Since \mathcal{T} grows exponentially with each additional parameter, exhaustively searching over every parameter configuration becomes quickly infeasible. On the other hand, an exhaustive search is guaranteed to find a global optimum $c_{\text{opt},k}$ for any given m_k . This strategy proves advantageous for efficient exploration of small search spaces or to conduct comparative evaluations of other search strategy (e.g how quickly they converge to the global optimum). Exhaustive search is frequently employed in studies focusing in a offline empirical autotuning context [52, 53].

Most of the time exhaustive search can also be called **grid-search** since it traverses over a J -dimensional discretized space forming a J -dimensional grid of parameters. However, not all grid-search approaches search exhaustively for every parameter configuration.

Random Search approach

In addition to the previously mentioned trivially implemented search methods, this approach samples a parameter configuration randomly at each iteration, forming a search space $\mathcal{S}_{\text{random}} \subset \mathcal{T}$, with $|\mathcal{S}_{\text{random}}| = N$, where each configuration c_i is independently drawn from a distribution \mathcal{D} (typically a uniform distribution). Random search does not make explicit restrictions on the search space.

Random search does not only serve as a baseline for comparison of Auto-Tuners against other more sophisticated search methods. It has been shown that random search in some scenarios outperforms grid-search [54] or advanced empirical search methods [55],[56]. The advantage of random search over certain more sophisticated methods in specific scenarios can be attributed to its ability to explore disconnected areas the of the search space. In contrast, local search strategies may become trapped in suboptimal regions early in the search process due to their limited exploration capacity.

Simulated Annealing

Simulated annealing (SA) is a probabilistic optimization algorithm originally inspired by the annealing process in metallurgy. The SA algorithm was first proposed to traverse large search spaces by Kirkpatrick et al. [57], drawing inspiration from physical cooling processes to escape local optima.

SA belongs to the category of local search algorithms that attempt to find a near-optimal solution within a large search space. It is particularly well known for solving complex combinatorial optimization problems, such as the Traveling Salesman Problem [57, p.9] (TSP), where an exhaustive search for the global optimum may take exponential time, whereas SA can often find good approximations in polynomial time, depending on the cooling rate and configuration parameters.

Early investigations of empirical auto-tuning struggled to demonstrate a significant advantage of using simulated annealing (SA) over random search as a search strategy [56]. However, more recent work, such as [19], has shown that SA can achieve better convergence rates and consistent improvements over random search for certain performance tuning problems. A potential explanation lies in the nature of the search space explored by Kernel Tuner [19], which often involves sparse spaces where only a small number of configurations yield high performance—for example, "only six configurations result in a performance above 3800 GFLOP/s" [19, p.352]. It is also important to note that Kernel Tuner allows users to specify the hyperparameters for the SA algorithm. Although the paper provides these parameters for a selected set of kernels, achieving optimal results typically requires manual tuning of hyperparameters such as the initial temperature and cooling rate for each new problem. As a result, replicating their promising results on different problems (and especially problem sizes) may prove difficult without proper adjustments to the tuning setup, effectively shifting the responsibility to the user.

SA introduces a *temperature* parameter T , which gradually decreases during the optimization process. This parameter controls the acceptance probability of worse configurations in early stages, allowing the algorithm to explore the search space broadly and escape local optima. As the temperature lowers, the algorithm increasingly favors configurations that offer local improvements, thereby focusing the search on promising regions.

Algorithm 1: Simulated Annealing

Input: Objective function f , initial solution s_0 , initial temperature T_0 , cooling factor α , stopping condition `stop_cond`

Output: Approximate solution s

$s \leftarrow s_0$;

$T \leftarrow T_0$;

while *not* `stop_cond`(T) **do**

$s_{\text{new}} \leftarrow \text{neighbor}(s, T)$;

$\Delta \leftarrow f(s_{\text{new}}) - f(s)$;

if $\Delta < 0$ **or** $\text{rand}(0, 1) < e^{-\Delta/T}$ **then**

$s \leftarrow s_{\text{new}}$;

$T \leftarrow \alpha \cdot T$;

return s ;

Explanation of Steps:

- **Initialization:** Start with an initial solution s_0 and initial temperature T_0 .
- **Neighbor Selection:** In each iteration, a neighboring configuration s_{new} is selected using a function that may also depend on the current temperature.
- **Evaluation:** The difference $\Delta = f(s_{\text{new}}) - f(s)$ is calculated, where f is the objective function (e.g., runtime or throughput).
- **Acceptance Rule:** The new configuration is accepted if it improves the objective or with a probability based on the Metropolis criterion if it does not.

- **Cooling:** The temperature is updated using a cooling schedule (commonly geometric: $T = \alpha \cdot T$, with $0 < \alpha < 1$).
- **Termination:** The process stops once a specified stopping condition is met, such as a minimum temperature or a fixed number of iterations.

An interesting aspect of simulated annealing is the selection of neighboring configurations. In the work of Yao et al. [58], the authors propose a method where the temperature directly influences the distance to neighboring points, allowing for broader exploration during early stages and more refined local search as the algorithm cools. This insight is particularly relevant when considering parameters with large value domains. In such cases, restricting transitions to immediately adjacent values may result in insufficient coverage of the search space, as the algorithm might get stuck in a local optima early during the tuning process.

Yao et al. [58] propose a simulated annealing strategy where the neighborhood size is dynamically adjusted according to the current temperature. In their approach, the probability of transitioning from the current configuration X to a candidate configuration Y is governed by a temperature-dependent probability density function $f(\xi)$, where ξ denotes the Hamming distance between X and Y . This design ensures that, at higher temperatures, configurations with larger Hamming distances are more likely to be explored, promoting global exploration. As the temperature decreases, the probability mass shifts toward smaller distances, favoring local refinement.

2.8 Related Work

Autotuning for hardware-related performance optimization has been an active field of research for decades, dating back at least to the ATLAS project [52], published in 1997, which applied empirical tuning techniques for matrix multiplication on microprocessors. Since then, research in autotuning has spanned a wide range of architectures, differing in scope, tuning objectives, and the employed search strategies. Although, to the best of the author’s knowledge, there is no unified classification scheme for autotuning, several works—including [59, pp. 123–127], [60, pp. 19–20], [61], and [19, p. 348]—propose individual classification schemes. In this work, we present a selection of four such categorizations. Note that these categories are not always mutually exclusive.

Execution requirement: Static and Empirical Autotuning

Mustafa [59] differentiates between *model-driven* and *empirical* autotuning. Since the term “model-driven” is later used in a different context to describe a particular class of search strategies, we adopt the alternative terminology **static** and **empirical**, respectively. This distinction is conceptually equivalent to Mustafa’s categorization in the context of what they describe as “version evaluation.”

- **Static:** In Lim et al. [62], a static analysis approach predicts near-optimal thread and block settings for CUDA kernels by analyzing instruction mixes, register usage, and occupancy, reducing the reliance on costly empirical autotuning. In Hu et al. [63], a polyhedral model is used to predict a suitable thread-block size for a given workload on a NVIDIA GPU. They showed that the thread-block size recommended by the CUDA-API is not always the best configuration.
- **Empirical:** This category includes all approaches that rely on empirical data gathered through execution. Specifically, it includes any method that requires running one or more programs or benchmarks to construct a model or improve performance based on observed runtime characteristics. Zhang et al. [64] represent a case study in empirically tuning GPU grid and thread-block sizes for 3D stencil codes. In their work, they found that selecting the number of thread-blocks had a greater impact on runtime than the number of threads per block.

Program execution stage

Schöne [60, pp. 19–20] identifies several stages in the program compilation and execution pipeline where autotuning can be applied. In this work, we focus on two of those stages: source code transformation prior to compilation and run-time adjustments during binary execution, as they are the most widely supported methods by contemporary tuning frameworks.

- **Source Code transformation:** The tuning process involves switching between source-code variants, sometimes requiring recompilation for each configuration. Other works such as [65] use code generators as part of the tuning process to produce code variants for performance evaluation. Source code optimizations may involve loop unrolling, changing tile size, or performing affine loop transformations. In Chen et al. [66], CHiLL is introduced: a modular approach to loop transformation and autotuning, focusing on source-to-source code restructuring such as tiling, unrolling, and vectorization. CHiLL generates transformed code variants that must be recompiled, following a compile-run-evaluate cycle using empirical performance measurements.
- **Run-Time adjustments:** Tuning does not require multiple code variants and is reduced to code parameterization in the form of tunable variables. These variables must be runtime-adjustable (e.g., changing their value during binary execution). For example, Filipovi et al. [67] use an alternative approach by utilizing hardware performance counters to accelerate convergence in GPU autotuning. Using collected HPC data, they construct problem-specific models that capture the relationship between tuning parameters and performance metrics. These models are designed to be portable across different GPUs and input datasets. They reported higher convergence rates compared to state-of-the-art search techniques.

Environment

The differentiation between online and offline tuning is well established in the literature [59], [61, p. 2].

- **Online:** Tuning is performed during actual execution in a production run, allowing adaptation to the specific runtime environment. For instance, Beyerer et al. [68] apply adaptive tuning to optimize inter-node communication and energy efficiency in multi-GPU systems. A similar example is ytopt [69], an online autotuning framework designed for hybrid MPI/OpenMP applications on large-scale HPC systems such as Theta (Cray XC40) and Summit (IBM Power9 + NVIDIA GPUs). ytopt employs Bayesian optimization with a random forest surrogate model to explore large parameter spaces during execution, optimizing both performance and energy. Another prominent example is Active Harmony [70], which performs parameter tuning and algorithm selection without recompilation. Their work focused on CPUs and used a Nelder-Mead simplex strategy to traverse the search space. Pfaffe et al. [71] introduce a hierarchical search and evaluated it on Polybench kernels, comparing it against Polly, Polly-ACC, and OpenTuner. Beyond measuring final performance, they examined amortized runtime, capturing how quickly tuning costs are offset by performance gains, an essential factor in online scenarios.
- **Offline:** Tuning is performed prior to deployment, typically during compilation or a warm-up phase that executes a set of benchmark runs before the main program. Prominent examples include domain-specific libraries such as ATLAS [52] and FFTW [53], which use empirical tuning to optimize linear algebra and fast Fourier transforms, respectively. A key distinction is that offline tuning does not account for the runtime overhead of the tuning framework, and the time required to obtain the best-performing configuration is of secondary importance.

Utilized Optimization Strategy

Lastly, supported tuning strategies are a recurring theme in the literature. Zhou et al. [72] distinguish between machine learning-based approaches and search-based strategies. Larger autotuning frameworks often support a broad range of these strategies, allowing users to select or combine multiple techniques.

- **Search-based:** Utilizes naive strategies such as exhaustive enumeration or random sampling, but can also employ local search algorithms. Many of the aforementioned works leverage empirical search strategies ([70], [64], [52], [53]). Another contribution in this area by Li et al. [73] introduces a "shrinking-sample algorithm" that strategically prunes the search space by focusing early on promising regions rather than exhaustively evaluating all configurations. Their method was compared to simulated annealing, particle swarm optimization, genetic algorithms, and exhaustive search. It achieved the best-found configuration in four out of seven benchmark kernels and required fewer iterations than methods with comparable performance.
- **Model-based:** Employs predictive models—such as decision trees, Bayesian optimization, or neural networks—to prioritize or select configurations. For example, Bergstra et al. [74] use boosted regression trees. Gocht et al. [75] apply reinforcement learning—specifically Q-learning—to adapt power and performance states (e.g., core frequencies) at runtime using a model-free strategy. Bjertnes et al. [76] present a machine learning-based approach to optimize thread-block sizes in CUDA kernels, using their previously published LS-CAT dataset [77], which contains over 19000 CUDA kernels and 5 million runtime measurements. Their model outperforms the naïve selection of the largest configuration (1024 threads) and demonstrates that block size has an average performance impact of about 6%. Lars et al. [78] also introduce a machine learning-based approach to thread-block size optimization in CUDA kernels.

The previously established taxonomy is applied in Table 2.5 to works from the literature that have a narrower scope or tuning objective, whereas Table 2.7 covers more generic frameworks. A textual discussion of these classifications follows. Table 2.7 also presents the classification of this work according to the same taxonomy, with further details provided in the Implementation Chapter 3 (in Section 3.6). We deliberately placed this classification in a separate table to emphasize that the presented framework is not yet directly comparable to the state-of-the-art autotuning frameworks listed above in terms of feature set and strategy support. This distinction is discussed in more detail in Section 3.7.

Table 2.5: Comparison of application- and domain-specific autotuners across classification axes, architecture/back-end, and evaluation benchmarks.

Name / Author	Online / Offline	Static / Empirical	Runtime / Source Code-adjust	Model-based / Search-based	Contribution	Architecture / Back-End	Benchmarks
	(On/Off)	(S/E)	(R/S)	(M/S)			
PARALiA[68]	On	E	R	M	App-specific BLAS tuner	Multi-GPU (CUDA)	DGEMM, cuBLAS ...
Bergstra et al.[74]	Off	E	R	M	Predictive tuner (regres. trees)	CPU	Filterbank correlation kernel
Connors et al.[78]	Off	E	R	M	Block size predictor (ML + counters)	GPU (CUDA)	Not specified
Filipović et al.[67]	Off	E	R	M	Kernel Tuner extension	GPU (CUDA)	GEMM, Convolution, N-body
FFTW[53]	Off	E	R	S	FFT autotuner	CPU	FFT kernels
Gocht et al.[75]	On	E	R	M	Energy-aware tuner (Q-learning)	CPU (HPC)	Kripke benchmark
Hu et al.[63]	Off	S	S	M	Polyhedral tuning strategy	GPU (LLVM Polly)	PolyBench
Li & Agrawal[73]	Off	E	R	S	Shrinking Sample Search	GPU (CUDA)	GEMM, Bilateral, Convolution
Lim et al.[62]	Off	S	R	M	Static performance predictor	GPU (CUDA)	Not specified
KTT Benchmark[79]	On	E	R	S	Benchmark suite	GPU (CUDA, OpenCL)	GEMM, BiCG, N-body, ...
ATLAS[52]	Off	E	S	S	BLAS autotuner	CPU	DGEMM, BLAS
Willemsen et al.[80]	Off	E	R	M	Bayesian Opt.	GPU (CUDA)	Not specified
Wu et al.[69]	Off	E	S	M	PolyBench autotuner	CPU (LLVM Polly)	syr2k, 3mm, covariance, heat-3d
Zhang & Mueller[64]	Off	E	S	S	Stencil autotuner	GPU clusters (CUDA/OpenCL)	3D stencil kernels

Generic Autotuning Frameworks

Autotuning has evolved from application-specific solutions, such as ATLAS for linear algebra on CPUs, to more generalized frameworks capable of optimizing a wide array of applications across diverse hardware platforms. These generic autotuners provide flexible interfaces and support various search strategies, architectures and back-ends. Notable examples include CLTune, OpenTuner, and Kernel Tuner [19], each offering unique features and capabilities. The works mentioned above including Active Harmony [70] and ytopt [69] are also counted toward the more generic approaches and therefore are included in the classification in Table 2.8.

Kernel Tuner is a Python-based autotuning framework to optimize GPU kernel performance, with support for both the CUDA and OpenCL back-ends [19]. It primarily relies on offline, non-static tuning, where candidate configurations—such as thread-block sizes, grid dimensions, and shared memory usage—are evaluated through empirical execution. Kernel Tuner performs runtime compilation via Nvrtc [?], avoiding full recompilation per configuration. The framework provides support for a wide range of tuning strategies such as gradient-based approaches, basin hopping, Bayesian optimization, and local search approaches such as genetic algorithm and simulated annealing. The original paper [19] focuses primarily on the evaluation and comparison between these search strategies. In a supplementary paper [80] they also implemented a specialized version of Bayesian optimization for the Kernel Tuner that showed promising results compared to the aforementioned methods.

CLTune [55] introduces a generic autotuner designed for OpenCL kernels, allowing the exploration of parameter spaces such as work-group sizes, vector widths and loop unrolling factors. The paper evaluates multiple search strategies, including exhaustive search, random search, simulated annealing, and particle swarm optimization. They effectively applied this framework in [55] to optimize 2D convolution and matrix multiplication (GEMM) kernels and demonstrated consistent performance improvements over the cBLAS [81] library.

GPTune [82] is a model-based autotuning framework built for HPC applications with expensive evaluation costs. It applies Gaussian process regression and multitask learning to share tuning knowledge across related problem instances. GPTune supports parallel evaluation and has shown improvements in tuning dense eigensolvers and quantum chemistry codes, outperforming traditional Bayesian optimization and random search. It is best suited for applications with high-dimensional tuning spaces and cross-task performance similarities.

OpenTuner [18] is designed to be as generic as possible, allowing its application for optimizing user defined parameters, OpenMP directives or LLVMs. Needless to mention it is capable of fine-tuning applications targeting any architecture or back-end. Unlike domain-specific autotuners, OpenTuner provides a flexible Python interface for defining parameters, objectives, and constraints. It operates in an offline, non-static fashion, relying on empirical execution to evaluate each configuration. It supports a diverse range of search techniques—such as genetic algorithms, hill climbing, particle swarm optimization, and Bayesian optimization—and dynamically selects among them based on their historical effectiveness during the tuning process (allocating more iterations on better performing strategies).

The **Kernel Tuning Toolkit** (KTT) [17] is a more recent C++-based autotuning framework for GPU kernels supporting CUDA, OpenCL, and Vulkan. It performs offline, non-static tuning by empirically evaluating kernel variants with different launch configurations and code parameters (e.g., tile sizes, vector widths). KTT is designed for cross-platform portability, making it suitable for heterogeneous systems. Most notably, it also provides an interface to describe customized constraints to express relations between tunable parameters. In Petrovic et. al.[79] the Kernel Tuning Kit [17] is used to optimize ten different benchmarks. It provides insights on how to extract more performance using general optimization techniques and utilizing the generic autotuning framework to find the optimal hyperparameters.

Table 2.6: Comparing "more" generic autotuning frameworks across classification dimensions, supported scopes, architectures, and evaluation benchmarks.

Name / Author	Online / Offline (On/Off)	Static / Empirical (S/E)	Runtime / Source Code-adjust (R/S)	Model-based / Search-based (M/S)	Contribution	Architecture / Back-End	Benchmarks
OpenTuner[18]	Off	E	R/S	M/S	Meta - Framework	CPU / GPU	Mario, compiler flags, sorting, FFT, ...
CLTune[55]	Off	E	S	S	OpenCL autotuner	GPU (OpenCL)	2D convolution, GEMM
Kernel Tuner[19]	Off	E	S	M/S	Framework for GPU Kernel tuning	GPU (CUDA, OpenCL)	GEMM, FFT, stencil, transpose, ...
KTT[17]	On/Off	E	S	S	Generic autotuner	GPU (CUDA, OpenCL, Vulkan)	Internal benchmark set
ATF [83]	Off	E	S	S	C++ Tuning Framework	GPU (CUDA, OpenCL)	GEMM, BiCG, N-body, ...
Active Harmony[70]	On	E	R	S	Runtime tuner	CPU	Not specified
GPTune[82]	Off	E	R	M	Heterogeneous cluster autotuner	HPC (MPI + CPU)	Eigensolvers, Quantum chemistry, PDEs
ytopt[69]	Off	E	S	M	Bayesian LLVM optimizer	CPU (LLVM)	PolyBench

Table 2.7: Classification of the alpaka Tuner based on the established taxonomy, using the same column headers as Table 2.8.

alpaka Tuner (this work)	On/Off	E	R/S	S	Autotuner in alpaka library	Multi-platform through (alpaka)	BabelStream, Stencil-Code, CLUE
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3 Implementation

This chapter outlines the core implementation and design decisions of the proposed tuning framework, which is designed as an integrated extension of the alpaka library. The framework aims to address the practical challenges related to embedding performance tuning in a performance-portable parallel programming model, with minimal disruption to the existing abstractions of alpaka.

3.1 Design Goals and Decisions

Generality Generality is a foundational objective of the tuning framework, extending alpaka’s philosophy of abstraction across heterogeneous hardware. While alpaka enables portable kernel execution across back-ends, optimal performance still depends on hardware-specific parameters, algorithmic characteristics, and problem sizes. Therefore, the tuner must be capable of identifying high performing configurations across varying execution contexts—including different back-ends (e.g., CUDA, HIP, OpenMP), architectural features (e.g., core counts, memory hierarchies), and problem descriptions (e.g., computational intensity, data access patterns). To meet this challenge, the framework adopts an environment-aware tuning approach. Rather than attempting to find universally optimal configurations, it explicitly performs tuning only for the current execution context—defined by the active kernel, back-end, hardware. This ensures that the best configuration is tailored to the conditions under which it will be used. Furthermore, hardware resource checks are incorporated to constrain and shape the tuning space and based on the execution back-end.

Modularity The tuning framework is designed to operate on top of alpaka without interfering with its general workflow. It avoids altering core mechanisms and instead builds as an optional layer that extends existing functionality. While efforts were made to minimize dependencies on alpaka, the framework relies on several utilities and helper functions provided by the library. However, these dependencies are non-fundamental, ensuring that the core tuning logic remains conceptually decoupled from alpaka’s internal architecture.

Integration The framework is designed to integrate seamlessly into the alpaka 3 user interface, minimizing the overhead required to enable tuning. This is achieved by closely mirroring existing alpaka functionality and concepts, allowing users to adopt tuning features through interfaces that are already familiar.

Transparency Transparency is central to the tuning framework’s philosophy: the user remains in control of the tuning process at all times. Tuning is not handled by an opaque background optimizer—instead, it proceeds explicitly, one configuration at a time, whenever a kernel is enqueued. This design naturally supports **online tuning**, making the process both observable and interactive.

3.2 Architecture and Design

Before presenting the details of specific features, we begin with a high-level view of the framework’s architecture. As illustrated in Figure 3.2, the system can be divided into five main components or aspects. These components work together to enable the configuration, execution, and evaluation of tunable kernels and their parameters. In the following subsections, we examine in more detail, outlining their roles, and implementation choices.

Figure 3.1: Top-Level architecture diagram of the proposed framework

Configuration and User Interface

The configuration component hosts the tuning builder interface, as well as the compile-time tuning trait definition. A Tuning Session is the central orchestration unit, which manages and monitors the tuning process (this is explained in more detail later in Section 3.2). The builder class can be used to define a tuning-session, using the builder pattern [84].

Listing 2 shows an example excerpt of how a tuning session can be configured by the user. The builder pattern enables users to iteratively add configuration options, even though most of them have sensible defaults, which means that extensive definitions are typically unnecessary.

Among other settings, the user can specify the output file where performance evaluations are persistently

```
// Example: configuring a tuning session
using namespace alpaka;
auto tuningSession = tune::TuningBuilder{}
    // specify output file name
    .withConfig("config_file_name")
    // strategy selection
    .withStrategy(tune::strategy::randomSearch{})
    // define tuning objective
    .withMetricInterface(tune::interface::timing{})
    // example of using custom values for the thread-block size
    .withThreadBlockSizeTune(tune::Tunable{Vec{8,8},Vec{16,16},Vec
        {32,32}})
    // let tuner decide suitable values for numBlocks
    .withNumBlocksTune()
    // express a logical constraint between parameters
    .withConstraint<ID1, tune::frame::numBlocks>([[ auto a, auto b) {
        return b.x() % a.x() == 0;
    }])
    .build();
```

Listing 2: Example: configuring a tuning session

stored, the metric interface and strategy which will be used during the tuning phase, and specific parameters within the frame specification, which are supposed to be part of the tuning process, can be enabled and defined.

The builder can be used to define tuning-parameters used in the frame specification (such as `thread-BlockSizeTune` and `numBlocksTune`). In the subsection 3.3 the interface to define tuning-parameters is discussed in detail.

Finally, the Listing also illustrates how the user can define relations between two tuning parameters, which can be used to enforce correctness as parameters vary during tuning. This helps ensure that only valid combinations of parameter values are evaluated.

In this example, the constraint is defined using a lambda function that operates on two tunables. The framework supports both predefined IDs (e.g., for `frameSpec` parameters such as `numBlocks`) and custom IDs for runtime or compile-time tunables. **Metric Interface** The tuning session allows customization of the optimization metric the tuning-mechanism tries to minimize or maximize. By default, the tuner uses time-to-solution as the target metric. A custom metric can be provided by implementing a class that defines both a start and an end method. The start method is called prior to kernel execution and after completion of kernel execution. The end method is expected to provide the measurement corresponding to the current run. In addition, the custom interface must specify how to compare two configurations—i.e., whether higher or lower values are considered better. By default time-to-solution is used.

Strategy In contrast to more generic state-of-the-art tuning frameworks, this software provides only a limited set of built-in strategies, therefore the strategy interface allows extending the set of provided strategies. The strategy is defined by a functor (`operator()`), it is expected to provide one new parameter configuration on invocation. The functor takes multiple parameters such as the metric interface, tuning parameters, and search history. Event though this allows incooperating new strategies, uture work might be necessary to make this interface especially the provided parameters more intuitively understandable to the user.

Constraints In many tuning scenarios, not all parameter combinations are semantically valid or meaningful for kernel execution. To address this, the framework allows users to specify constraints – logical conditions that must be satisfied by candidate configurations during the tuning process. The framework uses compile-time IDs to reference individual tuning parameters (see Section 3.3). For frame-specific tunables (e.g., `numBlocks`, `numThreads`), predefined identifiers are provided in the `alpaka::tune::frame` namespace. Constraints are defined using lambda functions that take two parameters and return a Boolean value, indicating whether a given combination is valid. By default the tuning framework incorporates constraints, which ensures that `numThreads` is always smaller than `frameExtent` and `numBlocks` is always smaller then `numFrames`, as such configurations would result in the allocation of more workers than required for the given workload.

Tuning Context

The tuning context component addresses a challenge imposed by the existing User-Interface: maintaining and managing state across kernel invocations. Rather than instantiating a new tuning session for every kernel launch, sessions are ideally created once per program execution. However, when specific kernels are queued, their `FrameSpec`, the executor, or the target device are not natively associated with the session. This information only becomes available, when a kernel is enqueued.

Certain operations, such as extracting runtime parameters from a `KernelBundle`, should not be repeated for every step. Instead, we want a setup phase that captures this context once and makes it available during the tuning process.

This is the role of the Tuning Environment. It holds all relevant state information for a kernel context. It tracks:

- Device and executor

- Frame specifications and runtime tuning parameters
- All metric measurements associated with a given kernel
- The Config Queue (which holds active parameter configurations)
- An instance of the active tuning strategy

The `TuningEnvironment` object is specialized per session signature, `enqueue`-call and optional runtime specifiers. This allows the framework to support multiple active tuning contexts—even within the same session. It also allows strategies to maintain the state tied to specific kernel invocations.

Tuning Process

The tuning session is the main logical module of the software design, orchestrating components to select profitable or not yet evaluated tuning parameters for the current context.

Figure 3.2: Flow diagram of the tuning process

The process is best described as a visualization in Section 3.2. The tuning session first retrieves the tuning environment for the enqueued kernel and generates a new tuning configuration, if necessary, through the strategy interface. Moreover, it applies the generated tuning configuration to the current `frameSpec` and runtime parameters, launches the kernel and retrieves the performance measurement through the Metric Interface, each step is modularized in separate function routines.

I/O

The tuning history handles writing of the combined available tuning contexts into a unified `.toml` file using the publicly available `toml11` library [85] (specified in `tuningSession` creation). Furthermore, this history can be reapplied on a program restart leveraging information acquired on previous program executions. The tuning history is structured as follows:

- **Top-level key:** A unique hash key. This key identifies a specific kernel-device-executor-metric combination.
- **target Metric:** The performance metric being measured (e.g., `time`, `energy`).
- **kernel:** A fully-qualified name of the kernel being tuned, including template instantiations.
- **executor:** The alpaka executor used.
- **device:** The alpaka device instance on which the kernel was executed.
- **specifiers:** Optional specifier assigned to the session at runtime (restricting the tuning context further to specific array sizes or data types).
- **configs:** An array of result entries, each representing one tuning parameter configuration:
 - `tuneableNames`: A list of tuning parameter names (e.g., `NumBlocksTune`, `FrameExtentTune`, `CTune_0`).
 - `tuneableVals`: A list of values used for the corresponding tuning parameters (encoded as strings for structural consistency).
 - `stamp`: An integer timestamp for the tuning run.
 - `metric`: An array of floating-point values representing repeated measurements of the target metric for the given configuration.

alpaka API

The tuning-mechanism uses the `alpaka::enqueue` function of the corresponding queue that was already specified in Section 2.5, in order to schedule kernels with their adjusted parameter configuration for execution. In order to accurately measure timings (as this is the default metric interface), it is necessary to synchronize Host and Device afterwards (ensuring that the device successfully finished execution). This is an important distinction from the general workflow alpaka, where the user must explicitly request synchronization between host and device.

3.3 Tuning Parameters

In the following section, we introduce the concept of *tuning parameters*, which can be used to optimize the alpaka kernels. These parameters represent values that the tuning system can systematically vary to find high-performing configurations.

All runtime-tunables are constructed from the same base class, offering a flexible interface with multiple constructors. A typical tunable parameter is created by specifying an initial value, a discretized range (start, end, stride), an optional identifier, and an optional policy to control multi-dimensional behavior.

Listing 3.1: Example definition of a multi-dimensional tuning parameter.

```

auto threadblock = Tunable<ID1>(
  IdxRange(Vec{8, 4}, Vec{16, 8}, Vec{8, 4}), //IdxRange
  /*      start      end      stride      */
  Vec{8, 4}, //initial Values
  "threadExtent", //name
  DimensionsDependent{} //Policy
);

```

The arguments for the constructor are as follows.

- `IdxRange` Constructs a discrete and linear tuning space using a start, end, and stride vector. The range is inclusive, meaning that both the start and end points are part of the generated tuning space. The range must consist of `alpaka::Vec`'s, which provides an n-dimensional vector, which can wrap any primitive type and provides arithmetic and Boolean operations.
- `ID` – Optional tuning ID. Required only when using this parameter in constraint definitions.
- `init` – Optional starting value.
- `"threadExtent"` – Optional tuning name, the tuner assigns a unique name in the default case.
- `DimensionPolicy{}` – Optional policy that specifies whether each vector dimension should be tuned independently. If specifying `DimensionsIndependent`, which is also the default, each dimension is treated as a separate parameter during the strategy phase.

A second constructor uses a `std::initializer_list` instead of a `IdxRange`, which can be used to describe any tuning space (extending the linear `IdxRange` definition), similar to those found in other tuning frameworks such as Kernel Tuner [19] or ATF [83].

Categories of Tuning Parameters

The framework distinguishes between three types of tunables, based on where and how they are applied.

User defined Tunables

User-defined tunables represent values that are explicitly passed to the kernel at runtime. It is the user's responsibility to ensure that such parameters are indeed tunable—that is, they should influence performance without affecting the correctness of the algorithm. This mechanism provides a high degree of flexibility for incorporating application-specific tuning logic.

Listing 3.2 illustrates the use of user-defined parameters in a kernel invocation and a standard kernel invocation `alpaka` (without tuning). In both cases, the parameter will be interpreted as a single-element floating point vector within the kernel. The listing also highlights the structural similarity between the standard `alpaka` interface and the tuning framework's interface with regard to the `enqueue()` function.

Listing 3.2: Using a runtime parameter in an `alpaka` kernel.

```
//standard alpaka kernel enqueue
auto parameter = alpaka::Vec{1.0};
queue.enqueue(exec, frameSpec, KernelBundle{Kernel{}, parameter});
//tuner kernel enqueue using a runtime parameter
auto tuning_parameter = Tunable{IdxRange{1.0,10.0,1.0}};
session.enqueue(queue, exec, frameSpec, KernelBundle{Kernel{}, tuning_parameter});
```

Compile-Time Tunables

Compile-time tunables allow users to tune kernel parameters that affect code generation and would traditionally require recompilation. These include factors such as loop unrolling, tiling sizes, and SIMD widths—parameters that influence the structure of the compiled kernel itself.

To enable compile-time tuning, the user provides a specialization of a trait for the corresponding kernel. The kernel must be templated accordingly so that the tunable type becomes part of its signature and can influence compilation.

Internally, the framework generates all valid instantiations of the kernel for the specified tuning parameter values before program execution. During tuning, the system selects among these precompiled variants at

```

namespace alpaka {
    template<typename TuneableParam> // the template CTunable defines
    struct CompileTimeTuneableTrait<CompileTuneExample<TuneableParam>> {
        // indices of tuning parameter(s) in kernel signature
        static constexpr auto tuned_indices = CVec<int, 0>{};

        // definition of compile-time tuning parameters for CompileTuneExample
        static constexpr auto tuneAbleDefinitions() {
            constexpr auto tunable = tune::CTunable<
                CVec<int, 16>, // first value
                CVec<int, 32>, // second value
                CVec<int, 64>, // third value
                CVec<int, 128> // fourth value
            >{};
            return std::make_tuple(tunable);
        }
    };
}

```

Listing 3: Trait specialization example for enabling compile-time tuning in the `CompileTuneExample` kernel

runtime, based on a subset of the currently selected parameter configuration. In order to make compile-time tunables compatible with the same interface used for runtime parameters, the specified compile-time tunables get converted to a runtime variant, allowing a unified treatment of all tunables within the tuning framework.

An example of a trait-based definition for a compile-time tunable using a one dimensional tuning-space is shown in Listing 3.

The trait consists of two components. First, the `tuned_indices` member specifies the positions within the Kernel 2.5 signature, that are to be substituted with values from the corresponding compile-time tunables. Second, the `tuneAbleDefinitions` function must return a tuple of `CTunable` instantiations. The order of elements in this tuple directly corresponds to the order of indices specified in `tuned_indices`, thereby determining which tunable replaces which position in the kernel's template signature.

Each `CTunable` defines a set of configuration values using alpaka's `alpaka::CVectors`. These vectors may represent multidimensional parameter spaces; in the example provided, a one-dimensional `CVector` is used. Kernel instantiations are generated for all combinations of these configuration vectors. Additionally, a tunable may include an optional ID to include the specified tuning parameter in constraint relations, similar to the mechanism used for runtime tunables. While compile-time tuning parameters offer powerful opportunities for performance optimization by enabling kernel specialization during compilation, they can also significantly increase both compilation time and binary size. This overhead becomes especially pronounced when multiple kernels and large tuning parameter spaces are involved, as all possible combinations must be instantiated and compiled in advance.

Frame Specification Tunables

Frame specification tunables allow the user to tune the components of alpaka's `Frame` configuration, which can be used to define the index space and by modifying the `ThreadSpec`, contained within the `FrameSpec` the user may also influence the number of participating workers. These tunables must be registered during session configuration.

The following components of the frame specification can currently be tuned:

- `withNumFramesTune()` – Total number of frames to process
- `withFrameExtentTune()` – Number of elements per frame

- `withNumBlocksTune()` – Number of thread-blocks
- `withThreadBlockSizeTune()` – Number of threads per block

Each of these functions accepts a corresponding `Tunable` object, which defines the search space for that dimension of the frame. The complete interface for configuring these tunables, along with constraints and tuning strategies, is presented later in ???. There, we illustrate how frame-related tuning objects are integrated into the session setup process. By default, every provided tuning object gets automatically truncated to the valid range defined by the provided frame specification. This prevents the exploration of invalid or infeasible configurations during the tuning phase.

Frame Specification Tuning Defaults and Resource-Aware Space Adaptation

When a tunable object is not explicitly provided, the tuning system automatically derives a reasonable search space from the given `ThreadSpec`. For each tunable frame component—such as the number of frames, frame extent, number of blocks, or thread-block size—the framework generates a valid tuning range based on both user input and back-end-specific hardware limits. This includes clamping the range to avoid invalid configurations and choosing a suitable start and stride to reduce tuning cost.

In the case of thread-block-related tunables (`withNumBlocksTune()`,

`withThreadBlockSizeTune()`), the tuner incorporates hardware-aware resource partitioning.

Scalar hardware resources—such as the number of multiprocessors (on GPUs), cores (on CPUs), or wavefront execution units (AMD-GPU’s)—are first factorized into primes and then distributed across the dimensions of the tuning vector using a round-robin strategy, with preference given to faster-varying indices. The same applies for the block-size where the hardware specific warp size (usually) or wavefront size is used as to be distributed across dimensions.

This allows the tuning space to consist of hardware-aligned configurations—i.e., multiple of the warp size or compute unit count—leading to better scheduling, higher occupancy, and reduced divergence. On CPUs, similar reasoning applies to matching the number of threads to the available physical cores to avoid resource under-utilization. A related treatment of warp-aligned tuning for stencil codes is described in [64].

The upper bound for `numBlocks` values is defined by the `numFrames`, therefore the tuning space for `numBlocks` can become very large—when selecting the number of multiprocessors or cores as the stride, especially for large problem size. As a consequence, the framework automatically restricts the number of `numBlocks` parameter to lie below 32 configurations by default.

Furthermore an environment variable: `TunerMaxConfigs` can be specified, which enables user-defined control over the maximum number of configurations T . When `TunerMaxConfigs` is set, an adaptive tuning space reduction strategy is applied: parameter values are pruned (e.g. by removing odd-indexed candidates) iteratively from the tuning parameter that hosts the most values. This ensures manageable tuning complexity, which is especially critical for exhaustive search strategies.

Adaptive shrinking tuning space

The tuning space $T = \tau_0 \times \dots \times \tau_J$ (see Section 2.7 for the formal definition) can be reduced on request by the user. If the environment variable `TunerMaxTuningSpace` is set to a target T_{\max} , the alpaka tuner performs an automatic pre-shrink: it repeatedly selects the parameter domain with the most candidates and discards every second value (odd indices), recomputing $|T|$ after each step and stopping once $|T| \leq T_{\max}$ or a domain has fewer than two values. This keeps the search tractable while preserving validity constraints and broad coverage across parameters. *Note.* The final size is bounded by $|T'| \leq T_{\max}$ but is not guaranteed to equal T_{\max} ; due to discrete down-sampling, $|T'|$ may fall below the target (often within $T_{\max}/2 < |T'| \leq T_{\max}$).

Figure 3.3: Timing distribution collected by executions of the stencil kernel from the *HeatEquation* benchmark 5.3. The plot shows the distribution of 1000 consecutive kernel-duration measurements on an AMD EPYC 9334 CPU and an NVIDIA H100-SXM5-94GB GPU, respectively.

3.4 Noise – And its implications on the Autotuning Framework

This section should give the reader a short introduction in the fallacies of performance benchmarking on computational devices and how it affects critical design decision with regard to the tuning framework. Data quality is an important aspect of performance tuning that is often overlooked. To the best of the authors knowledge among the generic autotuning frameworks listed in Table 2.8, only Kernel Tuner explicitly states how many times each configuration is measured before accepting the result: it defaults to seven executions, with the number being user-configurable [19]. Although PARALiA [68], which has been classified as a domain-specific online tuning framework reports the use of a 95% confidence interval threshold during its offline warm-up phase, ensuring a bounded relative error before proceeding. Yet empirically measured benchmarks are subject to varying noise levels that cannot be fully excluded by the experimenter. This means that certain configurations might be classified as low performing while in reality the system load varies. Certain maneuvers to ensure reproducible results can be taken by setting the frequency to a certain level, restricting thermal throttling and reducing the probability of context switches. Removing these side-effects is practically unfeasible in any online tuning process. Given that the tuning framework proposed in this thesis is designed to execute scientific workloads in real-world computing environments, we have to quantify the uncertainty produced by a system under test.

Figure 3.3 illustrates an extreme example of timing noise, collected without pinning CPU frequencies or cores and without performing any warm-up runs. While this setup deliberately exaggerates performance variability to expose worst-case behavior, it still reflects realistic scenarios in real-world environments. The benchmark operates on a data-size of 2 GiB, resulting in median runtimes of approximately 33.7 ms on the CPU and 2.15 ms on the GPU. These durations represent meaningful workloads in many scientific applications. In fact, smaller problem sizes would significantly exacerbate timing noise (which is later illustrated by Figure 5.3c).

The figure presents timing data for two devices: an AMD EPYC 9334 CPU and an NVIDIA H100-SXM5 GPU. In both cases, the observed distributions deviate substantially from a normal distribution. For the GPU, 48.9% of samples fall between -1σ and 0σ , 6.6% between -2σ and -1σ , and 3.1% exceed $+2\sigma$, with nearly 2.0% above $+3\sigma$. The CPU results are even more skewed: 66.0% of samples lie between -1σ and 0σ , with 23.1% between $+1\sigma$ and $+2\sigma$, and no samples beyond $+3\sigma$.

These asymmetries suggest instability across both devices, particularly in the CPU data, which shows a clear bimodal distribution. Only 7.5% of CPU samples fall between 0σ and $+1\sigma$, but over three times

as many (23.1 %) cluster in the next bin, hinting at distinct performance regimes—likely from warm-up effects when threads are scheduled on cold cores.

To mitigate the impact of unstable behavior and transient performance spikes, the first measurement of each configuration is discarded. This accounts for system-level warm-up effects that affect both CPU and GPU timing.

Finally, given the non-normal and left-skewed nature of the distributions, **minimum runtime** is not a reliable or reproducible metric. Instead, we adopt the **median** as a robust alternative to compare parameter configurations. When working with the median, Hoefler et al. [86] recommend using a confidence interval threshold $CI_\alpha < n$ on the median to estimate the number of required evaluations. This approach aims to reduce the variance in the measurement of individual parameter configuration, was also adopted by [87] in their autotuning framework. The in this work presented tuning-mechanism also includes this as a stopping criteria for parameter configuration evaluation. Furthermore Hoefler et al. [86] discuss how individual performance measurement should be compared, recommending approaches such as the nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis [88] test for non-normal distributed data. The Kruskal–Wallis test is a rank-based nonparametric method to test whether samples originate from the same distribution. It determines whether there is a statistically significant difference between the medians of multiple independent groups. Since low-performing parameter configurations do not necessarily require enough evaluations to reach the confidence interval threshold, we apply a Kruskal–Wallis test between the current and the best-known configuration. If the test indicates with statistical confidence that the current configuration performs worse, it is discarded.

Breaking Criteria

Several types of stopping criteria have been discussed in the autotuning literature, often involving queue-based or convergence-driven heuristics. In this work, we distinguish between three classes of stopping conditions:

Local Break Criteria This criterion determines when to stop evaluating a single configuration. As discussed earlier, this is based on the confidence interval thresholds on the median and the Kruskal Wallis Test. If the runtime estimate becomes statistically stable (e.g., $CI_\alpha < n$), further evaluations are considered unnecessary. Further, an environment variable `TunerRunsPerConfig` can be provided, which overrides these methods to enforce a fixed number of evaluations.

Global Break Criteria The global breaking criteria mark the point, where the evaluation process of the tuning framework is no longer active. Once the global criterion is met, only the best configuration observed during tuning is executed. While the global stopping criteria are not fully customizable (unlike, for example, [19], which exposes a dedicated interface for user-defined stopping conditions), the global stopping condition defaults to either (i) the maximum number of parameter configurations or (ii) a user-defined environment variable `TunerMaxConfigEvaluations` (which is based on the number of valid configurations that were executed).

Strategy Break Criteria Certain search strategies (e.g., stochastic or random search) may fail to explore new configurations for a number of consecutive iterations. If this occurs and no global environment variable has exceeded the maximum evaluation limit, the strategy break criterion gets activated. This will result in the global break criteria getting triggered as well.

Environment variables to adjust the breaking criteria The tuning mechanism provides several environment variables that allow the adjustment of the tuning space and breaking criteria during runtime:

- `TunerRunsPerConfig` – Overrides the default local break criteria by enforcing a fixed number of executions for each parameter configuration, regardless of statistical convergence.

- `TunerMaxConfigEvaluations` – Sets an upper bound on the total number of **valid** configurations to be evaluated, overriding the default global break criterion.
- `TunerMaxTuningSpace` – Defines a maximum tuning space size T_{\max} . If the initial space $|T| > T_{\max}$, the tuner automatically applies the adaptive shrinking process (see Section 3.3) to reduce $|T|$ until $|T| \leq T_{\max}$.

Configuration Queue

While estimating the median performance of a specific parameter configuration in a statistically sound way helps mitigate the most significant effects of system-induced noise, it does not guarantee stable estimates over longer periods of time. This is because system conditions—such as frequency scaling or varying system load—can fluctuate over time. As a result, measurements collected during one time window may not accurately reflect the true performance of a parameter configuration under ideal or controlled (ISO) conditions, especially if different configurations are evaluated under different system states. To reduce the impact of such fluctuations during the tuning process, the system queues up to a predefined number of parameter configurations. Each configuration is evaluated consecutively for n runs—typically including one or more warm-up runs followed by actual measurement runs (e.g., one warm-up and one actual evaluation)—before proceeding to the next configuration in the queue. This approach deliberately spreads the evaluation of each configuration over a longer time period rather than executing all runs consecutively under very stable conditions. By exposing each configuration to varying system states, comparability between configurations improves, as no single configuration disproportionately benefits from temporarily favorable system conditions. A configuration remains in the queue until its local stopping criterion is met, at which point it is dropped from further evaluation. The downside of a configuration queue that should be considered is that strategies are responsible for pushing configs into the queue, this means that the actual that gets evaluated is in most cases based of a decision that happens the length of the config queue before. In this prototypical stage, the configuration queue is set to host just 10 configurations, but this parameter should potentially be dependent on the system noise.

Implemented Search Strategies

While the presented software implements only a minimal set of search strategies compared to more advanced autotuning frameworks, it is designed to be easily extensible. This enables future integration of more sophisticated search algorithms with minimal structural changes. In general, whenever random numbers are necessary for a strategy: We use a `std::random_device` [89] to obtain a non-deterministic seed. This seed is retrieved via a system call to `/dev/random` or `/dev/urandom`, which provide pseudo-random bytes. These are generated from an internal state seeded by operating system-level entropy sources such as interrupt timing or hardware events, which introduce true randomness into the system [90]. This `std::random_device` is then used to initialize a mersenne twister `std::mt19937` [91] engine. This engine is subsequently used to generate values from the required probability distribution.

Exhaustive Search In the implementation, exhaustive search operates by explicitly enumerating all configurations within the tuning space $T = \tau_0 \times \tau_1 \times \dots \times \tau_J$ (as defined earlier). This is accomplished by incrementing a one-dimensional index and mapping it deterministically to a configuration $C \in T$. Specifically, the index is interpreted as a position in the Cartesian product, selecting values from each domain τ_j accordingly. To support flexibility, a compile-time flag `allowRandomInitialization` enables the search to begin at a randomly selected configuration $C_{\text{rand}} \in T$. From this starting point, the algorithm proceeds exhaustively, wrapping around as needed to ensure all configurations in T are eventually evaluated. By default (without defining this strategy starts at the index defined by the starting values (optional `init` argument) of each tuneable 3.3) or if `non` is present it starts at the highest value of each parameters defined tuning space.

Random Sample At each iteration, a configuration is drawn uniformly at random from the search space. In order to achieve that each parameter draws a random index defined from a `std::uniform_int_distribution`, which consists of all values of its own (typically user-defined parameter space).

Random Explore: This strategy basically combines the above methods. It first samples a configuration at random and if that calls the exhaustive search strategy, which is then used to traverse the search space starting from the initial index until a not-yet encountered parameter configuration is found. Both of the above strategies have their drawbacks, exhaustive search is highly dependent on the starting configuration and might struggle to find a good configuration early on since it might start in a local optima. Random search on the other hand might be able to find good configurations early on, yet it might struggle to cover the whole search space and might even ultimately fail due to the strategy break criteria being reached, this might be undesirable behaviour in very long tuning sessions.

Simulated Annealing: We implement simulated annealing (SA) with a temperature-dependent neighborhood selection strategy, inspired by Yao et al. [58]. Starting from an initial configuration, the algorithm explores the tuning space by generating neighbors at Hamming distance ξ , sampled from the exponential distribution $f_T(\xi) = e^{-\xi/T}$. High temperatures favor larger jumps; low temperatures focus the search locally.

The temperature T decreases according to a logarithmic schedule: $T = T_{\text{init}} - (T_{\text{init}} - T_{\text{final}}) \cdot \log(1 + r) / \log(1 + R)$, where r is the number of completed evaluations and R is the maximum. Both T_{init} and T_{final} are hyperparameters.

At each call to the strategy interface:

1. Sample $\xi \sim e^{-\xi/T}$;
2. Randomly mutate each selected parameter using a symmetric temperature-dependent distribution over its value domain (also based on f_T);
3. If the configuration is new, return it;
4. Otherwise, accept with probability $\min(1, e^{-\Delta E/T})$.

To maintain continuity across runs, this same acceptance rule is applied at the start of each tuning session to decide whether to resume from the last returned configuration (that was not yet evaluated in the last iteration).

3.5 Feature Summary

- **Context-Aware Tuning**

The execution environment—including device, executor and kernel type is tracked to establish a unique tuning context, as these typically exhibit different performance behavior and require separate optimal configurations. This design ensures that performance measurements are contextualized heterogeneous workloads and computing devices.

- **Persistent Tuning History**

Evaluation results are stored in a structured `.toml` file, allowing configurations and their associated metrics to persist across program runs. By reloading this history during startup, the tuner can resume where it left off and reduce redundant evaluations.

- **Constraint System**

Logical constraints between tunables can be defined using lambda expressions, referencing built-in or user-defined IDs. Invalid parameter combinations are discarded, ensuring semantic correctness of executed configurations.

- **Metric Interface**
Optimization objectives are decoupled from kernel execution via a customizable metric interface. Users can define their own start/stop hooks and comparison logic, supporting both built-in metrics like execution time and application-specific alternatives such as energy or occupancy.
- **Extensible Strategy Interface**
Search strategies are encapsulated in functor-style objects that emit new configurations based on internal logic and search history.
- **Per-Configuration Evaluation Logic**
Each configuration is evaluated with optional warm-up runs, repeated measurements, and statistical analysis. The framework uses the median as the default performance metric and applies confidence interval checks and nonparametric tests (e.g., Kruskal-Wallis) to mitigate system noise.
- **Configuration Queue**
Parameter configurations are maintained in an active queue and evaluated in an interleaved manner. This design exposes each configuration to a broader range of system conditions, improving robustness against transient performance fluctuations.
- **Frame-Aware Tunables**
Frame specification parameters such as `numFrames`, `frameExtent`, `numBlocks`, and `numThreads` can be parameterized with minimal overhead allowing adjustments of the index space and number of workers during runtime.
- **User-Defined Runtime Tunables**
Arbitrary values passed to kernels at runtime can be declared as tunable, provided they are wrapped in `alpaka::Vec` and support arithmetic and Boolean operations. This allows the user to include domain knowledge into the tuning process in order to optimize problem-specific variables.
- **Compile-Time Tunables**
Template-based kernel parameters can be tuned through trait specialization. The tuner generates all kernel variants ahead of time and selects among them at runtime, allowing code generation-dependent optimizations such as tiling or loop unrolling.

3.6 Categorization

The proposed tuning framework **alpaka Tuner**—can be positioned along the classification axes introduced in Section 2.8. Table 2.7 in Section 2.8 includes a supplementary entry that positions this work alongside others in the literature, based on the established taxonomy. Here, we provide the context and rationale for this classification in a more pertinent section, now that the design and implementation have been described. **Environment: Online and Offline Usage**

The framework supports both offline-style and online-style tuning workflows. For offline usage, users may perform a dedicated tuning run and store the best-known configuration in persistent history files, which can be reloaded in subsequent executions. For online usage, tuning can be integrated into the beginning of a production run, after which the best configuration is used for the remainder of the program. Repeated re-tuning—e.g., in response to known phase transitions within a simulation—can be implemented manually by changing session specifiers.

Execution Stage: Runtime Adjustments and Source Code Transformations

The alpaka Tuner supports both runtime and compile-time parameter tuning. Runtime tunables include user-defined kernel arguments and alpaka `FrameSpec` components such as thread-block size or number of blocks. Compile-time tunables are supported through trait-based kernel specialization, enabling source-level transformations such as loop unrolling or tiling. All valid instantiations are compiled ahead of time, and selection is performed at runtime based on the current configuration.

Execution Requirement: Empirical Tuning with Static-Informed Defaults

All configuration evaluations are performed empirically through repeated kernel execution. However, the tuning system incorporates static hardware knowledge (such as warp size, number of SMs, or CPU cores) to generate meaningful default ranges, especially for thread and block-level tunables. This hybrid strategy improves effectiveness of tuning, while remaining measurement-driven.

Optimization Strategy: Search-Based with Extension Interface

The current implementation includes only search-based strategies such as random search and exhaustive enumeration. However, the strategy interface is fully extensible, allowing users to integrate custom or model-based strategies. Strategies operate as functor-style objects and can maintain state across kernel invocations.

3.7 Software Limitations and Outlook

Tunable Parameters - ranges and types

In theory, it is possible to tune any type or object that implements standard arithmetic and Boolean operators (+, -, *, /, %, &&, ||). However, such types must be wrapped in an `alpaka::Vec`, even in the one-dimensional case. This additional wrapping can make the syntax harder to read and interpret, especially when a scalar representation would suffice. Moreover, this design introduces a stronger dependency on the alpaka library. In particular, future changes to the implementation of `alpaka::Vec`, or the removal of this class entirely, may lead to incompatibilities or runtime errors when using the alpaka-Tuner. This tightly coupled behavior reduces the portability and long-term robustness of the tuner unless adjustments are made to align with upstream changes in alpaka.

Lazy constraint validation

Most tuning frameworks, such as those presented in [19] and [83], construct the full tuning space before initiating the search strategy. In practice, this means that all possible combinations of tuning parameters are generated and stored in memory before any evaluation is executed. While this is a necessary requirement for generating compile-time variants, it is not necessary for FrameSpec parameters or custom runtime parameters. However, the construction of the full tuning space allows for fine-grained analysis of the inter-dependencies imposed by the specified constraint relations. More specifically, configurations deemed invalid by the specified constraints can be pruned prior to the tuning process. In [92] the authors of the ATF [83] framework construct a tree-based approach that tracks and stores the inter-dependencies between tuning parameters more efficiently, allowing constraint relationships to be evaluated while a subset of the search space (containing valid configuration) is constructed instead of the full Cartesian product. A key downside of this approach is that in dense search spaces with many constraints, the probability of proposing invalid configurations increases. This can lead to premature termination if the search strategy's stopping criterion—typically defined by a fixed number of consecutive failed attempts—is reached.

Synchronization

As mentioned in Subsection 3.2, the device and host are synchronized after each kernel execution. This is a key distinction from the general execution model of alpaka, where the user must explicitly request synchronization. However, in the tuning context, it is enforced by default in order to guarantee the correctness of performance measurements. While it is theoretically possible to omit synchronization after tuning is completed—i.e. when the best configuration has been selected—this is currently avoided to prevent non-transparent behavior for the user. In future work, the entire tuning session (specifically the enqueue handling) could be offloaded to a background thread. This would make the tuning process asynchronous with respect to the calling thread, while still enforcing host-device synchronization internally.

Such a design would allow the main thread to continue issuing kernels on other queues without blocking on tuning-related synchronization.

Strategy Evaluation and Selection

The tuning framework presented in this thesis currently supports only a very limited selection of tuning strategies. Moreover, it lacks a mechanism for automatically selecting the most appropriate search strategy based on tuning context-specific criteria. This limitation is addressed in other systems such as OpenTuner [18] and ATF [83], which employ a multi-armed bandit approach to dynamically adapt the search strategy during tuning. OpenTuner [18] in particular uses a AUC Bandit approach, which selects tuning strategies based on how often they produce new *best* results, using a sliding window and a credit score derived from recent history. While integrating a similar mechanism would undoubtedly enhance the flexibility and performance of the presented framework, its implementation was not feasible within the time constraints of this project.

Fixed Final Configuration

Once a globally optimal configuration is found, it is fixed for the remainder of the execution. While this may be sufficient for short-lived or stable workloads, many real-world systems are subject to time-varying conditions, differing input buffer sizes and system load. Brunzema et al. [93] introduce a variant of Bayesian Optimization called *Time-Varying Bayesian Optimization* (TVBO), which is designed for settings where system behavior changes over time. Another approach that was integrated in OpenTuner [18], to effectively select strategies, is the multi-armed bandit method. Traditional multi-armed bandit (MAB) algorithms are effective for balancing exploration and exploitation based on historical rewards. However, they struggle when arm performance changes over time — Nobari [94] addresses this by introducing the Dynamic Bandit Algorithm (DBA), which adapts quickly to shifting trends using a time-aware reward model. Such model-based techniques could be employed to adapt the selection of evaluation strategies even after the global break criterion has been reached. Yet, this should act more as an outlook to reader, since in general it is possible to create more advanced options in user space.

4 Experimentell Setup and Methodology

The three main computing platforms were already introduced in Section 2.7. To address system-specific details more thoroughly, we now provide an in-depth overview of the software specifications and the underlying infrastructure.

4.1 Test Systems

The benchmarking for both the multiprocessor system and the NVIDIA GPU was carried out on a single node of the Capella cluster [46], with only one NVIDIA GPU used at any time. In contrast, the AMD measurements were performed on a separate system that features a different host processor configuration. Table 4.1 provides details on the hardware configurations and architecture of both systems. Table 4.2 outlines the software configurations, specifically for the exact alpaka execution back-end and device setups on which the tuning results in Chapter 5 were obtained. It also lists the relevant `slurm` settings used on the Capella Cluster for each corresponding alpaka back-end, to increase the reproducibility of the results presented. Note that on the NVIDIA-GPU setup - Although the Slurm job was submitted with `-gres=gpu:4` on the Capella cluster, alpaka was explicitly configured to select only one GPU device. This was done purely to ensure the job ran exclusively on that GPU without interference from other workloads—not to use multiple GPUs. For measurements conducted on the Capella cluster, we used `slurm` to limit the CPU frequency `-cpu-freq=high` to 2.7 GHz. However, empirical measurements indicate that the frequency consistently exceeds this threshold, operating at the boost limit (see Table 4.1). Thread pinning was enabled via `-cpu-bind=cores` for all measurements carried out on this cluster.

4.2 Methodology

All timing measurements were conducted using `std::chrono::high_resolution_clock`. Unless otherwise specified (e.g., in Section 5.5), all reported timings in the following chapter are obtained using the tuner’s built-in, TOML-based configuration generated after the tuning process concludes. All measurements are obtained in nanoseconds granularity. These values represent the performance of each configuration and, by default, do not include the runtime overhead introduced by the tuning mechanism itself.

However, the timing measurements include overheads from the `enqueue` and `wait` operations. The `enqueue` function initiates an asynchronous thread that submits work to the device, while `wait` introduces additional overhead due to host-device synchronization.

For CPU measurements using the alpaka OpenMP backend, we set the following environment variables:

```
export OMP_PLACES=cores
export OMP_PROC_BIND=true
```

This setup ensures that OpenMP threads remain bound to specific cores, therefore reducing the overhead from thread migration. Performance measurements for individual configurations report the 99 % confidence interval (CI), as discussed in Section 3.4.

Table 4.1: Hardware configuration of the two test systems. The NVIDIA-based system (*capella*) is used for benchmark runs with multiprocessor back-end support in alpaka.

System	AMD System (Hal)	Capella
Host		
CPU Model	AMD EPYC 7452	AMD EPYC 9334
Microarchitecture	Zen 2	Zen 4
Sockets / SMT	1 / Enabled	2 / Disabled
Cores / Threads	32C / 64T	64C / 64T
Base / Boost Clock	2.35 / 3.35 GHz	2.7 / 3.91 GHz
L2 / L3 Cache	512 KiB / 128 MiB	1 MiB / 256 MiB
NUMA Domains	8	8
Main Memory	8 x 32 GiB, DDR4-3200 Samsung M393A4K40DB3-CWE	12 x 32 GiB DDR5-4800 per socket
Motherboard	Supermicro H12SSL-i	Lenovo SB27B41167
OS / Kernel	Ubuntu 22.04 / 6.8.0	AlmaLinux 9.4 / 5.14.0
Accelerator		
Model	AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX	NVIDIA H100 SXM5
Architecture	RDNA3 (gfx1100)	Hopper (SM 90)
Compute Units	96 Compute Units	132 SMs (of 144)
VRAM	24 GiB GDDR6	94 GiB HBM2e
Bus / Interface	384-bit / PCIe	SXM5
L0 / L1 / L2 Cache	16 KiB / 256 KiB / 6 MiB	Instr. / 128 KiB / 50 MiB
Compiler Stack	LLVM 17.0 / GCC 11.3	CUDA 12.8 / GCC 13.3

Table 4.2: Software configuration across and additional settings for the alpaka execution backends (used in Chapter 5).

Alias	CPU	NVIDIA - GPU	AMD - GPU
Backend	OpenMP 4.5	CUDA 12.8.0	HIP 6.1.40092
Accelerator	AMD EPYC 9334	NVIDIA H100 SXM5	AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX
OS	AlmaLinux 9.4	AlmaLinux 9.4	Ubuntu 22.04
Kernel Version	5.14.0-427.33.1.el9_4	5.14.0-427.33.1.el9_4	6.8.0-65-generic
Core Layout	56C / 56T, no SMT [0-5,8-13,16-45,48-61]	2C/2T [0,1] (NUMA 0)	32C / 64T, SMT on
Compiler	GCC 13.3.0	NVCC 12.8 / GCC 13.3	Clang 17.0 / GCC 11.3
Flags	-O3 -march=native	-O3	-O3
alpaka Dependency	alpaka_DEP_OMP	alpaka_DEP_CUDA	alpaka_DEP_HIP
alpaka Executor	CpuOmpBlocks	GpuCuda	GpuHip
SLURM Settings	-nodes=1 -cpu-bind=cores -cpus-per-task=56 -cpu-freq=high	-nodes=1 -cpu-bind=cores -cpus-per-task=2 -exclusive -gres=gpu:4 -cpu-freq=high	-

5 Benchmarks and Results

In this chapter, the previously described tuning framework is evaluated using a series of benchmark applications. These benchmarks include the well-known *BabelStream* benchmark [95], a simple 2D stencil heat-equation implementation, and a Poisson equation solver that demonstrates the use of runtime user parameters. Additionally, the CLUE algorithm [96]—used for clustering data in high-energy physics applications—is included as a more complex benchmark, featuring multiple kernel invocations.

We also include a brief, high-level description of each algorithm and the theory behind it, to provide context for the tuning process and help illustrate how the tuning parameters influence performance. It is important to stress that the scope of this chapter is *not* to investigate or explain the root causes of good or bad performance in detail. Determining such causes with confidence would require targeted, architecture-specific profiling and analysis—beyond the remit of this work. Brief remarks or hypotheses about possible performance causes are included and should not be interpreted as firm research conclusions. These comments serve only to give additional intuition and are independent of the main results.

5.1 Poisson Equation and SOR

We begin the evaluation with the classic two-dimensional Poisson equation, using it as a simple, self-contained case to introduce the capabilities of the tuning framework. Unlike later benchmarks, which involve multiple parameters tightly coupled to the underlying hardware architecture, this example focuses on a single, algorithm-specific tuning parameter. By starting with a conceptually simple, we aim to illustrate the tuning process, the integration of user-defined parameters, and the ability to adapt the search strategy to a well-defined mathematical target. Subsequent sections will build on this foundation, progressively introducing more complex scenarios with multiple interacting parameters, stronger links to architectural details, and larger tuning spaces. The Poisson equation is a partial differential equation (PDE) that describes equilibrium behavior in a variety of physical systems (e.g. fluid pressure fields) [97, p. 152, Ch. 6]. It is given by:

$$\boxed{\nabla^2 \phi = f}$$

where ϕ is the scalar potential and f is a source term. The discretized version of the Poisson equation can be solved iteratively using methods such as Gauss-Seidel or its accelerated variant: **Successive Over-Relaxation (SOR)** [98].

Relaxation Parameter ω

SOR introduces a relaxation parameter $\omega \in (0, 2)$ to accelerate the steps necessary to converge. The SOR update rule including the over-relaxation factor ω is given by:

$$\phi_{i,j}^{(k+1)} = (1 - \omega) \cdot \phi_{i,j}^{(k)} + \omega \cdot \left[\nabla^2 \phi_{i,j}^{(k)} - f_{i,j} \right]$$

For $\omega = 1$, the method is equivalent to the standard Gauss-Seidel scheme. For $1 < \omega < 2$, the method performs *over-relaxation*, effectively "overshooting" the current solution estimate in a certain direction. This direction is determined by the **residual**, which measures how far the current estimate is from satisfying the discretized Poisson equation. Specifically, the residual at a given grid point is defined as the difference between the left- and right-hand sides of the equation:

$$\text{residual}_{i,j} = f_{i,j} - \nabla^2 \phi_{i,j}^{(k)}$$

A small residual indicates that the current estimate is close to the true solution.

The optimal choice ω_{opt} depends on the spectral properties of the iteration matrix associated with SOR. Modifying the problem—for example, by scaling the diagonal of the system matrix with a factor λ —alters these spectral properties and shifts ω_{opt} . This relationship is discussed in detail by Varga [99, Section 4.3].

In our context, the tuning problem is formulated as finding the ω_{opt} that minimizes runtime while ensuring convergence to within a prescribed tolerance ε . Divergent runs — where the residual norm fails to meet ε within the maximum allowed number of iterations — are detected and automatically discarded using a cutoff criterion, activated when the runtime exceeds the expected range. In such cases, the tuning parameter no longer strictly adheres to the formalism established in 2.7, as the correctness criterion is effectively violated. By detecting and excluding these scenarios from further exploration, we implicitly impose additional constraints on the tuning space, thereby ensuring that only configurations producing correct results are considered.

Each of these three steps is performed iteratively until the convergence criterion is reached.

1. **PoissonStencil:** Applies a discrete approximation of the Laplace operator (e.g., a 5-point stencil in 2D) and effectively performs the update step on the scalar field ϕ based on its neighboring values and the source term f . This is the main update rule in the Poisson equation. The concrete implementation is based on alpaka's *HeatEquation* StencilKernel.
2. **computeResidual:** Calculates the residual at each point in the grid, which quantifies the local error between the current approximation and the desired solution. Afterwards the total sum of all residuals is calculated. Hence the implementation closely resembles the alpaka reduce Kernel.
3. **Boundary:** Applies a boundary conditions to maintain physical correctness of the domain. In our case, we use Dirichlet conditions on the left and right boundaries—fixing the potential values to simulate a laminar flow profile and Neumann conditions on the top and bottom boundaries. The implementation was inspired by alpakas *HeatEquation* Boundary Kernel.

A comparable discretization and iterative solution strategy (for example, using Gauss-Seidel or SOR) is discussed by Griebel et al. [100, ch.3]. All of these functions are implemented as individual alpaka kernels, which run on a device (e.g CPU, GPU). To maintain compatibility with the existing tuning framework interface—which necessitates that a kernel is enqueued and that all tunable values are passed as arguments to that kernel, we wrap the device-side components inside a **host-side kernel**. This kernel serves as a control structure that receives the tuned parameters (in this case ω) and passes them to each kernel invocation, which is performed on the underlying device. Since each step of the Poisson solver has approximately constant execution time, the *total number of steps required to converge* (defined as the point where the residual falls below a given threshold) effectively determines the overall runtime. Consequently, the default *timing-based metric interface* serves as a suitable cost function for this tuning problem. Nevertheless, it would also be possible to define a custom metric interface that directly measures the number of steps.

To approximate the optimal relaxation parameter ω_{opt} with high accuracy, the *iterative narrowing search* is implemented here as a custom strategy, made possible by the extensible strategy interface of the tuner. The method proceeds as follows:

Algorithm 2: Adaptive Narrowing Search for Optimal ω **Input:** Initial interval $[k, \ell]$, evaluations per iteration i , resolution factor r **Output:** Approximated optimal relaxation parameter ω_{opt} $p \leftarrow \ell - k;$ **while** not converged **do**

Construct a set of i uniformly spaced ω values in the interval $[k, \ell]$;
 Evaluate each candidate using the Poisson solver (timing-based cost);
 $\omega_{\text{best}} \leftarrow$ candidate with lowest cost;
 $k \leftarrow \omega_{\text{best}} - \frac{p}{r};$
 $\ell \leftarrow \omega_{\text{best}} + \frac{p}{r};$
 $p \leftarrow \ell - k;$

return $\omega_{\text{best}};$

We initialize the search procedure with an initial interval $[k, \ell] = [1, 2]$, discretized into candidate values using a uniform stride of 0.1. This results in an initial candidate set of 11 equidistant ω values, which serve as the basis for the first evaluation round.

Figure 5.1 shows the tuning process of the over-relaxation parameter ω across 100 iterations. In each iteration (x-axis), the solver runs as many steps as needed to reduce the residual below a target threshold or terminates early if the solution diverges or fails to converge within the allowed steps.

In Figure 5.1a, the adaptive narrowing search behavior is clearly visible: the tuner begins with a coarse sweep over the interval $[1.0, 2.0]$ and gradually refines its search around the most promising value. This process continues until the optimal parameter is identified with high precision (approximately to the third decimal place). Beyond this point, increasing the number of tuning iterations yields no further improvement, as the minimal number of solver steps has already been reached.

The corresponding performance evolution is shown in Figure 5.1b. Here, the runtime per configuration is plotted, where lower values indicate faster convergence. For scaling factors $\lambda = 0.9998$ and 0.9995 , several early ω values result in divergence or cutoff, reflected by plateaued timings around 0.15 s. As the tuning progresses, the search converges to optimal regions with runtimes around 0.076 s and 0.105 s, respectively. For $\lambda = 1.0$, the best performance is achieved, with the solver converging in approximately 0.068 s.

This experiment demonstrates that the alpaka tuner can effectively optimize a **user-defined algorithmic parameter**—in this case, the relaxation factor ω —to minimize the execution time for a domain-specific

(a) Convergence of the overrelaxation parameter ω toward its optimal value over successive iterations. The value of the best-found ω_{final} for each λ is indicated on the right.

(b) Convergence of the execution time toward a lower performance bound as tuning progresses over iterations.

Figure 5.1: Performance tuning of the 2D Poisson equation solver using Successive Overrelaxation (SOR). Each subplot tracks tuning progress across iterations for three distinct values of λ .

numerical method, by defining a custom search strategy which is designed to solve this problem with high precision. This experiment could be further enhanced by defining a step-based metric interface. In conclusion this result highlights the flexibility in targeting higher-level performance knobs.

5.2 BabelStream

BabelStream is a collection of small memory-bandwidth intensive benchmarks [95], it is open source and contains implementations for various programming languages and back-ends. Although our evaluation uses an alpaka-based implementation of the *BabelStream* benchmarks, the core computations remain consistent with the official versions. This makes it a suitable choice for performance comparison, as the results can be meaningfully contrasted with for example the official CUDA version provided in the *BabelStream* repository. Although the implementation of the *BabelStream* benchmark in alpaka supports both single-precision and double-precision runs, we conducted only single-precision measurements. The benchmark contains five kernels, all of which are predominantly performing read/write operations on one-dimensional memory buffers.

1. **Add Kernel:** $C[i] = A[i] + B[i]$ (2 load + 1 store)
2. **Copy Kernel:** $C[i] = A[i]$ (1 load + 1 store)
3. **Multiply Kernel:** $C[i] = A[i] \times B[i]$ (2 load + 1 store)
4. **Triad Kernel:** $C[i] = A[i] \times \text{scalar} + B[i]$ (2 load + 1 store)
5. **Dot Kernel:** $\sum_i A[i] \cdot B[i]$ (2 loads)

The kernels `Add`, `Copy`, `Mult`, and `Triad` follow a nearly identical decomposition strategy. Each worker (thread) operates on a subset of the global index space (in this case defined by the buffer extent), iterating over this subset using the `makeIdxMap` utility. The kernels are using the `SIMD::Algo` abstraction, which enables each thread to process a small bundle of aligned elements. These SIMD bundles ensure efficient memory access and potentially provide data-level and instruction-level parallelism across both the CPU and GPU back-ends (see Section 2.5).

Despite relying on the `FrameSpec` abstraction at launch time, these kernels do not directly use the `FrameSpec` structure within the kernel body. Instead, only the total number of workers is controlled by the associated `ThreadSpec` parameters.

The implementation of the `Dot Kernel` is a bit more nuanced. A dot product inherently involves a reduction operation—the summation of pairwise products between two vectors. To perform the reduction operation the sum is computed on several levels of the parallel hierarchy. This not only aims to incorporate efficient use of several forms of parallelism (see Section 2.1), but also to improve floating-point stability.

1. **Thread-level reduction:** Using `SIMD::Algo`, each thread reduces a group of elements, where the group-size is determined by the SIMD width and cache-line alignment. The partial result is written to shared memory.
2. **Frame-level reduction:** This effectively reduces the size of a frame (defined by the `frameExtent`) to the size of a block (`numThreads`).
3. **Block-level reduction:** A tree reduction is performed over the shared memory buffer using synchronized threads within the block.
4. **Grid-level reduction:** The final results per block are globally accumulated into a single output value using atomic operations. This step completes the full reduction across all blocks in the grid.

The following variables can be parameterized across all five kernels and serve as tuning parameters:

1. **numBlocks** Frame tunable parameters (see Table 2.2 and 3.3).
2. **numThreads** Frame tunable parameters (see Table 2.2 and 3.3). Notice that this tuning parameter gets internally disabled on CPU back-ends.

3. **ConcurrentElements**

This is a compile-time tuning parameter, which corresponds to `SimdConcurrencyBytes`, discussed in Section 2.5. It impacts the number of SIMD packs each worker processes. Internally, `SimdConcurrencyBytes` is derived by multiplying `ConcurrentElements` with the size of the data type (in this case `float`). When the resulting byte width is smaller than the architecture-specific SIMD width, this parameter also determines the SIMD pack size.

Additionally, the `Dot`-kernel is extended to support an additional tuning parameter, the `frameExtent`, which directly corresponds to dynamic shared memory allocation and indirectly increases the computational workload per thread.

Table 5.1 presents the specific tuning parameter values used for the benchmark.

Table 5.1: Tunable parameters for *BabelStream* Benchmark across all five Kernels.

Parameter	Add	Copy	Mult	Triad	Dot
<code>concurrentElements</code>	1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64				
<code>numThreads</code>	64, 128, ..., 1024 (stride 64)			64, 128, ..., 512 (stride 64)	
<code>frameExtent</code>	None			64, 128, 256, 512	
<code>numBlocks</code>	See Appendix A.2				

To gain insight into the structure of the tuning space, we performed an exhaustive search across all configurations. Figure 5.2 provides an overview of the resulting performance landscape across different hardware platforms. Since the performance measurements depicted in Figure 5.2 are normalized relative to the default configurations, these defaults are listed in the Appendix for reference. The default configurations used for comparison are listed in Table A, corresponding to an `arraySize` of 2 GiB. When analyzing the plots, a large spread along the y-axis generally indicates that the corresponding tuning parameter has a significant performance impact. In contrast, flat horizontal trends suggest that the parameter has little to no influence on performance. Starting with the CPU architecture 5.2a, we observe that most tuning parameters have negligible performance impact, particularly for the non-`Dot` kernels. The performance plateau especially regarding the `extttconcurrentElements` tune, suggests that the compiler is effectively able to auto-vectorize these kernels, rendering the tuning space less influential. The `Dot` kernel, however, exhibits some variation, likely due to the reduction operation’s more complex memory access pattern. Specifically, configurations using one-element SIMD packs (e.g., `concurrentElements = 1`) appear to disable effective auto-vectorization, leading to performance penalties of up to 30%. Additionally, the unexpectedly poor performance of a `frameExtent` of 128 is not the result of exceeding the cache capacity, since even the largest configuration $512 \times \text{sizeof}(\text{float}) \times 2(\text{load}) = 4 \text{ KiB}$ is significantly smaller than the AMD EPYC 9934 L1 Cache. The performance of a `frameExtent` of 128 hints at more subtle cache-related issues, such as false sharing or unfavorable core placement.¹ The AMD GPU 5.2b stands out as the most responsive architecture to tuning in this benchmark. It is the only platform to achieve improvements of up to 20% over the default configuration, with a performance landscape that is both nuanced and diverse. For the `Dot` kernel, `concurrentElements` and `frameExtent` emerge as the most impactful parameters, whereas for the other kernels, both `numBlocks` and `numThreads`

¹Since `frameExtent` indirectly determines the memory access pattern of each thread-block by influencing the `blockStartIdx`. Although the mapping strategy (see 2.5) enforces a flat distribution policy, contention may still occur at domain boundaries, where adjacent memory blocks are accessed by thread-blocks assigned to cores from different NUMA-domains.

(a) CPU - AMD EPYC 9334

(b) AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX

(c) NVIDIA H100-SXM5

Figure 5.2: Relative performance (y-axis) of the best configurations for individual tuning parameter values across all kernels and architectures. Timing measurements conducted using the *BabelStream* Benchmark. Each point represents the best-performing configuration using a specific parameter value (x-axis), normalized against the default configuration. The best and worst performing values are labeled, with better configurations appearing higher in the plot and worse ones lower. In this experiment we used the buffer-size of: 2 GiB. A more detailed explanation on how this was calculated is provided in Appendix A.

sizes play a dominant role. Notably, a thread-block size of 1024 consistently yields the best performance in kernels that involve a $2 \text{ load} + 1 \text{ store}$ pattern. On the other hand, `numBlocks = 24576` and `numThreads = 64` are consistently among the worst-performing configurations. These consistent trends—both good and bad—suggest that the AMD GPU *BabelStream* tuning space is a suitable candidate for both offline and online tuning. In contrast, the performance landscape on the NVIDIA GPU 5.2c is relatively flat. No configuration delivers a substantial gain over the default. However, config-

urations with `concurrentElements = 1` tend to perform worse in the `Copy` and `Mult` kernels, likely due to performing 32 bit loads rather than the supported 128 bit loads, which are encouraged by the `SIMD::Algo` memory alignment. Overall, `BabelStream` is a memory-bound benchmark with limited computational intensity. This means performance is primarily constrained by main memory bandwidth (especially with an array-size of 2 GiB). Configurations that might be suboptimal in compute intensive workloads, do not lead to significant performance degradation, as memory operations already dominate execution through frequent instruction stalls. As a result, even inefficient compute configurations may complete their work in time before new data becomes available. Moreover, since the memory access pattern is governed by `alpaka`'s default mapping strategy—which was not modified—its influence further constrains the observable effects of tuning.

Having established an understanding of the tuning performance landscape for a fixed `arraySize` of 2 GiB, where relative performance differences revealed the influence of various parameters—we now expand our evaluation. In the following experiment shown in Figure 5.3, we perform exhaustive tuning across a range of `arraySize` values and compare the achieved memory bandwidth of the default configuration against the best-tuned version. For the best and default configuration 1000 consecutive measurements were performed after the tuning process finished. Although scientific workloads typically involve kernel runtimes in the range of 1 ms to 10 ms—corresponding to larger buffer sizes such as 1152 MiB and 2048 MiB—the inclusion of smaller configurations in this evaluation remains valuable. These configurations help reveal architectural behavior near cache boundaries, where memory hierarchy effects, compiler optimizations, or system-level noise—such as scheduling artifacts, frequency scaling, or P-state transitions—can dominate performance. Such conditions pose a more challenging environment for the tuning mechanism, as configuration evaluations may reflect transient system states more than the intrinsic effect of parameter choices. This broader analysis offers insight into how tuning effectiveness varies not only with hardware—but also with problem size. In general, across all architectures, we observe that very small buffer sizes (2 MiB and, to some extent, 8 MiB) do not accurately reflect sustained memory bandwidth, since measurements are disproportionately affected by queue and synchronization overhead. For buffer sizes between 8 MiB and 32 MiB, caching effects become noticeable, as warm-up runs allow cache lines to remain partially or fully resident in the device's L1 or L2 caches, resulting in elevated bandwidth measurements within this range. For larger buffer sizes, this effect diminishes, as the majority of memory operations increasingly involve main memory rather than cache-resident data. This performance drop-off at larger buffer sizes is most pronounced on the AMD-GPU. Performance variability is also highest in the mid range around 32 MiB - likely near the L2 cache boundary - where most architectures and kernels exhibit the largest bandwidth spread, as reflected in wider box plots and a higher number of outliers. This experiment, conducted primarily on the CPU (see Figure 5.3a) and partially on the NVIDIA device, highlights one of the key limitations discussed in Section 3.7—namely, the use of a fixed final configuration. At a buffer size of 32 MiB, the default configuration significantly outperforms the best configuration selected during tuning. A time series analysis of both configurations revealed that the "best" configuration showed promising performance during the tuning phase (evidenced by outliers in the `Copy` and `Add` kernels), but exhibited a performance shift once tuning concluded and both configurations were evaluated over 1,000 runs. In summary, while tuning does yield minor improvements across architectures and buffer sizes, these gains are often diminished—particularly in the 8–32 MiB range—due to inconsistencies between the tuning phase (where only a small number of timing samples are compared) and the more stable performance seen in extended runs. For larger buffer sizes, however, the tuned configurations consistently sustain memory bandwidths close to the hardware's peak capability. `Nsight Compute` profiles on the NVIDIA GPU report that the `Dot` and `Add` kernels achieve approximately 95 % and 92 % of peak DRAM throughput, respectively (see Appendix A for the profiling methodology). In such a bandwidth-saturated regime, even small measured speedups indicate configurations operating at or near the architectural limit, demonstrating that the tuning process is at least able to match—and in some cases slightly exceed—highly efficient defaults.

(a) CPU - AMD EPYC 9334

(b) AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX

(c) NVIDIA H100-SXM5

Figure 5.3: Distribution of Achieved Bandwidth Across Hardware Architectures and Array Sizes for the *BabelStream* Benchmark. The y-axis shows achieved memory bandwidth, and the x-axis represents varying arraySize values. For each hardware architecture, the blue box plots correspond to the default configuration, while the orange plots represent the best-tuned configuration. Each distribution is based on 1,000 runs. Whiskers extend to 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR).

5.3 2D Stencil Code - Heat Equation

The *BabelStream* benchmark was included in this thesis as a representative open-source workload. However, as discussed above, the available tuning parameters have only a limited effect on this type of memory-bound kernel mix, especially considering the apparent performance boundaries imposed by the underlying architecture, which limited the tuning potential. This makes *BabelStream* a useful baseline for evaluating tuning responsiveness, but also highlights the need to examine workloads where com-

putational structure, data reuse, and synchronization patterns play a more prominent role. The next benchmark—the *HeatEquation*—addresses this need. Like *BabelStream*, it operates on regular grids but replaces the purely bandwidth-driven operations with a repeated stencil update pattern that interleaves computation and memory access more evenly. At the same time, it shares structural similarities with the previously introduced *PoissonEquation*, but instead of iterating toward a steady-state solution, it advances the solution forward in time through explicit time-stepping. This combination of temporal iteration and local stencil updates makes the heat-equation particularly well suited for exploring tuning parameters related to shared memory usage, tile size, and temporal blocking, where both computational structure and data locality strongly influence performance. Physically speaking, the heat equation describes the diffusion of thermal energy within a continuous medium. It is a partial differential equation that evolves a temperature field over time, capturing how local gradients in temperature drive heat flow. A general derivation of the heat equation, including its physical interpretation as a diffusion process, is presented in Pinchover and Rubinstein’s textbook [101, Chapter 1].

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \nabla^2 u}$$

Here, $u = u(x, y, t)$ denotes the temperature field, and ∇^2 is the Laplace operator, representing the sum of the second derivatives of u with respect to the spatial coordinates.

$$u_{i,j}^{(k+1)} = u_{i,j}^{(k)} + \Delta t \cdot \nabla^2 u_{i,j}^{(k)}$$

For the discrete form, $u_{i,j}^{(k)}$ denotes the numerical approximation of u at grid point (i, j) and time step k . For numerical treatment and computation, Langtangen and Linge [102, Chapter 3.6] provide a detailed exposition, where they present general implementations of the two-dimensional heat-equation using finite-difference schemes. Their implementation include both explicit and implicit (backward Euler) computation. We are using an explicit scheme, with the update Rule (2D):

$$\nabla^2 u_{i,j}^{(k)} \approx \frac{u_{i+1,j}^{(k)} - 2u_{i,j}^{(k)} + u_{i-1,j}^{(k)}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{u_{i,j+1}^{(k)} - 2u_{i,j}^{(k)} + u_{i,j-1}^{(k)}}{\Delta y^2}$$

As evident from the update rule, the heat-equation employs the same discrete Laplace operator used in the *PoissonEquation* to perform the stencil computation. From a programming perspective the benchmark consists of two primary computational kernels: a *boundary kernel* and a *stencil kernel*, analogous in structure to those used in the *PoissonEquation*. These kernels are executed consecutively for a fixed number of time steps. Since each time step represents a discrete forward integration in time by Δt , the total number of steps is determined by $t_{\max}/\Delta t$. The following pseudocode presents a compact implementation of the stencil kernel for the *HeatEquation* benchmark. Unlike the *PoissonEquation*, where the focus was on a user-defined runtime parameter and the algorithm executed until convergence, the *HeatEquation* allows us to focus on tuning the stencil kernel directly—this being the most computationally intensive component of the application.

Algorithm 3 outlines the steps executed by the stencil kernel in the heat-equation benchmark in detail. The `map` function used in Algorithm 3 corresponds to the alpaka mapping abstraction described in Section 2.5. The algorithm also leverages chunking and shared memory, enabling stencil computations to be performed on localized subregions of the input domain. This already resembles an optimization over a naive implementation that relies exclusively on global memory access. In this context, a chunk—or tile—of memory corresponds to a `Frames`, whose dimensions are defined by the `frameExtent` parameter. The pseudocode further illustrates where the two-dimensional tuning parameters—`frameExtent`, `numThreads`, and `numBlocks`—are used to control domain decomposition and expose parallelism at multiple hierarchical levels. Note that the algorithm produces correct results only if the parameter `frameExtent` divides the `arraySize` evenly in both dimensions. This constraint ensures that the

Algorithm 3: Pseudocode of the Chunked 2-D *HeatEquation* Stencil Kernel. **Bold** variables are subject to the tuning process.

```

Input: frameExtent, numThreads, numBlocks
Data: uCurrBuf
Output: uNextBuf
halo ← {2, 2};
sharedData ← getSharedMemory.sizeOf(frameExtent);
startIndices ←
  map((numBlocks, blockIdx) ↦ Range(0, uCurrBuf.size(), frameExtent));
foreach (frameX, frameY) ∈ startIndices do
  chunkIndices_withHalo ←
    map((numThreads, threadIdx) ↦ Range(frameExtent + halo));
  foreach (frameElX, frameElY) ∈ chunkIndices_withHalo do
    /* load chunk to shared memory */
    sharedData[(frameElX, frameElY)] ←
      uCurrBuf[(frameX + frameElX, frameY + frameElY)];
  synchronizeThreadsInBlock();
  chunkIndices ← map((numThreads, threadIdx) ↦ Range(frameExtent));
  foreach (borderI, borderJ) ∈ chunkIndices do
    /* Five-point stencil computation (shifted by halo) */
    (i, j) ← (borderI + 1, borderJ + 1);
    gIdx ← (frameX + i, frameY + j);
    ui,j ← sharedData[(i, j)];
    ui-1,j ← sharedData[(i - 1, j)];
    ui+1,j ← sharedData[(i + 1, j)];
    ui,j-1 ← sharedData[(i, j - 1)];
    ui,j+1 ← sharedData[(i, j + 1)];
    rX ← Δt/Δx2;
    rY ← Δt/Δy2;
    uNextBuf[gIdx] ←
      (1 - 2rX - 2rY) · ui,j + rX · (ui-1,j + ui+1,j) + rY · (ui,j-1 + ui,j+1);
  synchronizeThreadsInBlock();

```

input domain can be perfectly tiled without leftover regions or partial frames, which would otherwise cause out-of-bounds memory accesses or incomplete computations. Since the tuning framework supports user-defined constraints between parameters, this requirement must be expressed explicitly during the tuning process. By enforcing a constraint (see Section 3.2) on the divisibility of `arraySize` by `frameExtent` in both dimensions, the tuner is guided to explore only valid configurations that preserve the correctness of the kernel execution.

First, we take a look at the tuning space again to get a understanding how much influence each parameter has on the performance. Figure 5.4 illustrates how performance varies with different values of tuning parameters for the *HeatEquation* benchmark. Each point corresponds to the best-performing configuration using a particular parameter value (x-axis), with all other parameters allowed to vary freely. The full distribution of performance values is not visualized here. As such, seemingly implausible jumps (e.g., where all values show a minimum speedups above 2,5×) are the result of this best-case selection and not reflective of the entire performance distribution.

Across all architectures, we observe a clear and consistent improvement over the default configuration, with relative speedups ranging from roughly 40% on the CPU and NVIDIA GPU to nearly 3× on the AMD GPU. Among all tuning parameters, `frameExtent_x` has the most pronounced and consis-

Table 5.2: Tunable parameters for the *HeatEquation* benchmark across architectures, excluding `numBlocks`. Default values correspond to the configuration selected as Default for each architecture. The `numBlocks` configurations are found in Table A.2

Architecture	Parameter	Dim	Values	Default
AMD & Nvidia	FrameExtentTune	x	8, 16, 32	16
		y	4, 8, 16, 32	16
	ThreadBlockTune	x	8, 16, 24, 32	16
		y	4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32	16
CPU	FrameExtentTune	x	4, 8, 16, 32	16
		y	4, 8, 16, 32	16
	ThreadBlockTune	x	—	nan
		y	—	nan

tent impact on performance, followed by `numThreads_x` on the selected GPU targets. In contrast, `numBlocks` exhibits minimal performance sensitivity across all platforms, particularly on the CPU, where it yields an almost flat performance profile. This reinforces the insight that kernel configuration parameters closely tied to data access patterns—such as tile size and thread layout—are more influential than coarse-grained launch parameters such as `numBlocks` for this particular benchmark. In general, larger chunk sizes (i.e., greater `frameExtent`) lead to better performance. On the CPU, this can be attributed to improved spatial locality, more effective hardware prefetching, fewer loop nests. On GPUs, this effect is similarly evident but more tightly coupled to the underlying execution model. Across both AMD and NVIDIA devices, the configuration `frameExtent = (32, y)` consistently performs well. A Frames width of 32 in the x-direction aligns with memory coalescing requirements and warp-level execution semantics on NVIDIA GPUs. On the AMD Radeon GPU, the same value is a natural fit, as each Dual Compute Unit (DCU) contains two `SIMD32` units, allowing efficient execution of 32-thread rows within a 64-thread wavefront. In general, a higher `frameExtent` (while having a smaller thread-block size) increases instruction-level parallelism, since each thread is assigned more work—which is expected considering this benchmark remains predominantly memory-bound. In NVIDIA H100-SXM5 specifically, the configuration `numThreads = (32, 4)` allows a warp to process an entire row, while the y-extent of 4 aligns well with the number of warp schedulers per streaming multiprocessor (SM). Moreover, the `frameExtent = (32, 16)` configuration, which achieves the best performance on this architecture, further supports efficient resource distribution. Since one thread-block processes a single chunk, this configuration leads to four loop iterations per block, potentially reducing contention and shared memory bank conflicts by aligning the workload with the four scheduler pipelines of the SM. For the CPU backend, improvements are also observed, but are more limited, with speedups ranging from 1.1× to 1.4×. The most influential parameters are `frameExtent_x` and `frameExtent_y`, where increasing the tile size yields marginally better performance due to reduced loop overhead and better cache locality. Interestingly, the number of thread-blocks has minimal to no impact on CPU performance, resulting in a near-constant performance plateau. This can be attributed to alpaka’s contiguous memory mapping strategy for CPU backends, in combination with OpenMP’s default core assignment behavior - which eventually partitions the iteration space (`numBlocks.product()`) across all available cores. Both approaches ultimately assign nearly identical regions of the problem domain to the same physical cores.

Compared to the previously analyzed *BabelStream* benchmark, the *HeatEquation* benchmark exhibits a far more stable performance profile across all hardware platforms and buffer sizes. In the distribution plots (see Figure 5.5), the interquartile range (IQR) is often imperceptibly small, with most box plots collapsing into a single visible line. This indicates a high degree of measurement stability and minimal vari-

Figure 5.4: Relative performance of the best configurations for individual tuning parameter values, measured on the *HeatEquation* stencil kernel benchmark. Each point corresponds to the best-performing configuration using a specific value of the corresponding tuning parameter (x-axis), evaluated across all kernels and architectures. Performance (y-axis) is shown relative to the default configuration, with higher values indicating better performance. The best and worst parameter values are annotated (Figure 5.2 already used this approach on the *BabelStream* benchmark). Measurements were conducted using an array size of 16384 x 16384 elements. (2 GiB total). A detailed explanation on how this was calculated is provided in Appendix A.

ability between runs—particularly at larger buffer sizes. A modest number of outliers is observed across all three devices, predominantly for small array sizes (e.g., 8 MiB), where short execution times make the benchmark more sensitive to transient system noise. This pattern mirrors the behavior previously seen in *BabelStream*, although the variability here is notably lower. Importantly, for all devices, the best-tuned configuration outperforms the default configuration across every buffer size. On the AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX, the performance gains are especially substantial: the median speedup increases steadily from approximately 1,93× at 8 MiB to 2,88× at 2048 MiB. This trend is expected, as the relative impact of synchronization and kernel launch overhead diminishes with larger problem sizes—allowing the benefits of improved launch configuration to dominate the runtime, thus increasing the relative speedup. The NVIDIA H100-SXM5 shows a different trend. The achieved speedup is relatively stable across buffer sizes, starting at 1,34× for 8 MiB and settling around 1,25× from 512 MiB onwards. Unlike the AMD GPU, tuning on this platform provides immediate benefit even for small buffers, but exhibits diminishing returns at larger scales. This may suggest that the default configuration is already well-optimized for larger workloads, where it achieves a generally high occupancy. In contrast, smaller buffer sizes may expose alternative configurations that exploit faster launch-to-completion cycles or improved scheduler alignment—leading to higher relative gains during tuning. On the AMD EPYC 9334 CPU, improvements are more modest but still meaningful. For buffer sizes up to 128 MiB, performance gains remain marginal (approximately 1,12× or less), reflecting the limited influence of kernel configuration and synchronization overhead at these smaller scales. However, as buffer sizes increase to 512 MiB and beyond, the median speedup rises to 1,37× and peaks around 1,41× at 1152 MiB. Across all devices, the general trend established earlier—that the AMD GPU is the most sensitive to tuning—is consistently reinforced

Figure 5.5: Distribution of Achieved Bandwidth Across Hardware Architectures and Array Sizes for the *HeatEquation* Benchmark. The y-axis shows achieved memory bandwidth, and the x-axis represents varying arraySize values. For each hardware architecture, the blue box plots correspond to the default configuration, while the orange plots represent the best-tuned configuration. Each distribution is based on 1000 runs with the specified configuration. Whiskers extend to 1,5 times the interquartile range (IQR).

across buffer sizes. Whereas *BabelStream* only showed tuning gains for specific kernel patterns or parameter regions, the *HeatEquation* stencil kernel benefits more uniformly. This consistency is largely attributable to a higher compute intensity and an increase in degrees of freedom (two dimensions) per kernel launch parameter.

5.4 CLUE Algorithm

The CLUE algorithm [96] (Clustering of Energy) is a density-based clustering algorithm developed at CERN in the context of high-energy physics, specifically tailored for fine-granularity calorimeter data. It addresses the challenge of efficiently reconstructing particle showers in a detector consisting of millions of fine-grained silicon sensors. These sensors collect energy deposits in layers, and the goal is to group nearby hits into coherent clusters. From a physics standpoint, shower reconstruction requires grouping sensor hits that arise from the same particle as it traverses the calorimeter. Due to the detector’s high resolution, the number of hits per event can vary from thousands to millions, imposing challenging timing constraints on an algorithm that aims to process these events in real-time. The accompanying paper [96] details the algorithm design and shows promising results in meeting these constraints. CLUE distinguishes itself from traditional clustering algorithms, such as *k*-means, by not assuming a fixed number of clusters and by supporting the identification of arbitrarily shaped clusters and outliers. In the context of this thesis, CLUE represents a representative scientific workload that consists of multiple non-trivial compute kernels with different memory access patterns, algorithmic dependencies, and degrees of parallelism. Unlike the stencil-based *HeatEquation* benchmark or the memory-bound *BabelStream*,

CLUE introduces a more diverse computational pipeline and serves as a practical example for evaluating the capabilities of the hereby presented tuning mechanism.

A version of the official open source CLUE Algorithm [96], was fully implemented in alpaka. As in the original, it proceeds in several distinct stages, each of which maps to a dedicated GPU kernel or compute step. The following list summarizes the alpaka kernels that run during the execution of CLUE:

- **Kernel 1: ComputeHistogram** – Constructs the fixed-grid spatial index by dividing all 2D hit positions into spatial tiles. This grid is later used for neighborhood queries.
- **Kernel 2: ComputeLocalDensity** – For each point, computes the local energy-weighted density by summing contributions from nearby points within a cutoff radius d_c , using a configurable kernel (e.g., flat or Gaussian).
- **Kernel 3: ComputeDistanceToHigher** – Determines, for each point, the distance δ to its closest neighbor with higher density. This step establishes the follower/leader relationships used in clustering.
- **Kernel 4: FindClusters** – Identifies seeds and outliers by comparing local density and separation values against configured thresholds. Seeds initiate new clusters, while outliers and their descendant followers are later discarded as noise.
- **Kernel 5: AssignClusters** – Propagates cluster labels from seeds through chains of followers in a parallel manner, resolving all valid cluster assignments.

Even without in-depth knowledge of the kernel’s structure and design, it is possible to tune `numBlocks` and `numThreads` with minimal effort. This is because alpaka again uses a mapping 2.5 instead of using `thread-block` or `thread` indicies directly for all the CLUE kernel. As a result, the correctness of the algorithm remains guaranteed. With only two tuning parameters, the entire search space can be visualized as a heatmap, as shown in Figure 5.6. Since the original CLUE evaluation was performed using an NVIDIA GPU backend, we likewise selected the NVIDIA H100-SXM5 GPU to ensure methodological consistency and enable direct comparison with the reference implementation. All results presented in this section are based on the `toyDetector_10000` dataset provided in the original CLUE paper [96]. We first analyze each kernel individually—examining their tuning spaces and relative speedups—because the tuner operates at kernel granularity. We then broaden the scope to consider the combined runtime of all kernels, noting the actual contribution of each to the overall execution time. Finally, we assess the generalizability of the identified tuning configurations by cross-comparing the best configurations across multiple datasets.

Individual Kernel Performance

Observations from figure 5.6, make it evident that all kernels exhibit vastly different tuning spaces. This variation is primarily attributed to the distinct underlying algorithms, as well as to the constraints imposed by the `FrameSpec`, which limits the number of permitted configurations—particularly for `numBlocks`, and to a lesser extent for `numThreads`.

The `ComputeHistogram` (5.6a) and `FindCluster` (5.6d) kernels display similar structural characteristics in their respective tuning landscapes, despite differing in the actual range of valid `numBlocks`. In both cases, the majority of configurations yield speedups close to one. However, configurations falling below a specific curve—resembling an inverse proportional relationship between `numThreads` and `numBlocks`—result in significantly reduced performance. This behavior is due to a sharp drop in occupancy and device utilization when insufficient warps are supplied to the GPU’s schedulers. Notably, this deficiency can arise either from too few thread-blocks or too few blocks overall. These findings strongly underline that `threadBlocks` and `numBlocks` are strictly correlated; consequently, treating them as independent parameters during tuning may be suboptimal for achieving high performance.

The `ComputeLocalDensity` (5.6b) and `ComputeDistanceToHigher` (5.6c) kernels, in contrast, demonstrate more diverse and complex tuning landscapes. Interestingly, both achieve their peak performance at a thread-block size of 768, which is not a power of two—defying typical expert preferences for 256 or 512 threads per block. Although 512 threads still yield competitive performance, it falls short of the optimum in these cases. With appropriate `numBlocks`, the 768-thread configuration achieves up to a 20% improvement over the default. With a lower number of threads and thread-blocks, we observe the same emerging pattern as for the first two kernels, implying that with fewer threads, we are effectively underutilizing the available resources.

The `AssignClusters` (5.6e) kernel deviates from the trends observed in the other kernels. Specifically, its performance does not scale favorably with increasing numbers of thread-blocks. This anomaly is likely algorithm-specific: the optimal number of thread-blocks appears to be closely tied to the number of clusters detected, which in turn depends on the input data. A comparison of runtime distributions (cf. Figure 5.7) shows that this kernel dominates total execution time. Consequently, tuning this kernel yields the greatest impact on overall performance. The optimized version runs 2.4 times faster than the default configuration—though this improvement may simply reflect an initially suboptimal default setting.

In conclusion, each kernel presents a distinct performance landscape. In particular, in three out of the five kernels examined, the optimal configurations deviated significantly from the default provided by `FrameSpec`. Furthermore, it is important to emphasize that the configurations analyzed were derived from tuner defaults rather than manually defined search spaces. This means the explored parameter

Figure 5.6: Exhaustive Tuning Space Evaluation on CLUE Kernels on GPU - H100 - SXM5. X axis shows the number of thread-block’s. Y-axis shows the number of threads in a thread-block’s. The Speedup to median (color-axis) is taken from the individual medians of each Kernel (since the workload and tuning space is vastly different, also note that the color bar values are different in each Kernel better highlight color gradients for each Kernel. Please Note: In order to emphasize features near the global minimum, the colormap is non-uniform: gradients transition from blue to yellow to red, with the crossover point at yellow, corresponding to 80 % of the maximum achieved speedup.

space was inherently constrained. Remarkably, without any user intervention, the tuner already achieved substantial performance improvements. This highlights the capability of the tuning mechanism to deliver competitive results autonomously. By incorporating expert knowledge into the search space design and traversal strategies, even greater performance gains could be realized.

Overall Runtime Decomposition The runtime distribution shown in Figure 5.7 illustrates the relative contribution of each kernel—and its tuned counterpart—during execution of CLUE on the H100-SXM5 GPU. The `AssignClusters` kernel stands out as the primary factor for the overall speedup: because it both consumes the largest share of the total runtime in the default configuration and achieves the highest relative performance gains, it is responsible for the most significant reduction in end-to-end runtime, while `ComputeLocalDensity` and `ComputeDistanceToHigher` show smaller but still measurable performance gains. Tuning these components reduces the overall runtime from 1.785 ms to 1.122 ms—achieving a total speedup of 59%. It is important to note that these results reflect a single dataset and may vary depending on input characteristics.

Figure 5.7: Runtime distribution of individual kernels during the execution of CLUE on the H100-SXM5 Nvidia GPU. The bars represent the mean runtime across 50 runs for each kernel. Small whiskers at segment boundaries indicate the $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ (interquartile range), showing runtime variability across runs.

Generalizability of Best Configuration In Figure 5.8, we highlight the differences in optimal performance across three dataset variants. While the data points in these datasets share the same coordinates (consisting of x and y coordinates and together forming identical clusters in a 2D projection), they differ in their ordering within the dataset. The *normal* dataset reflects raw input, as it might be emitted from a detector or generated synthetically. The exact ordering mechanism depends on the diagnostics employed by the sensor and is not known to the author. However, inspection reveals a pattern in which points that are spatially close in (x, y) tend to be located near each other in dataset order (row index). The *ordered* dataset is purposely sorted: points are traversed along the y -axis in discrete layers, and within each layer they are sorted by x coordinate. These layers are then concatenated from the bottom to the top. Finally, the *shuffled* dataset represents a worst-case scenario for memory and cache locality. It is a random permutation of the same points, leading to irregular memory access patterns in which spatially close points (often part of the same cluster) are rarely stored near each other in memory.

We selected the three most relevant kernels. `AssignClusters` and `FindClusters` were excluded, since they are showing nearly identical tuning landscapes and therefore *Best*-configurations, across the three input datasets, this is expected behavior from the semantic perspective of the algorithm – these two kernel perform identical work at this stage of the pipeline. The heatmap in Figure 5.8 illustrates how performance generalizes across datasets when reusing the best configuration from one variant on the others, using the first three kernels. First, all three kernels show different optimal configurations across the three datasets. For `ComputeHistogram`, although each dataset yielded a distinct best configuration, the overall performance impact remained limited—consistent with the relatively flat tuning landscape observed earlier in Figure 5.6a. In contrast, `ComputeLocalDensity` and especially `ComputeDistanceToHigher` show significant discrepancies.

The *shuffled* dataset, in particular, exhibits a significant deviation, with a minimum observed performance loss of approximately 8% when applying its configuration to other datasets or vice versa. For example, transferring the best configuration from the *normal* dataset to the *shuffled* dataset can lead to non-negligible performance penalties of up to 30%. Conversely, using the *normal* configuration on the *ordered* dataset (or vice versa) results in only a maximum of 5% performance penalty, suggesting the workloads are more similar. Supporting this, two of the three kernels use the same number of threads between these two datasets.

It is worth emphasizing that we did not alter the input data size—only the ordering—yet entirely different best configurations emerged, with markedly different performance impacts on a given dataset. These changes in the "best" configuration, would be expected when changing array sizes (which auto-

Figure 5.8: Performance impact of cross-dataset configuration evaluation on the `toyDetector_10000` dataset variants. Each row (y-axis) represents the best-performing configuration selected on one dataset variant (shuffled, normal, ordered), evaluated on each of the target datasets shown along the x-axis.

matically alters the `FrameSpec` - as portrayed Listing 1 and as a consequence restricts the tuning space (Section 3.2), but observing it solely from a change in ordering is far less intuitive.

This highlights a critical challenge: when input ordering shifts, optimal tuning parameters often change with it, making a fixed *final best* configuration impractical unless the tuning context is restricted to a specific ordering. Although the current framework allows such restrictions via the `withSessionSpecifier` interface, this assumes that users can identify and encode all relevant input characteristics—a requirement that is both unrealistic and impractical. Future work should therefore focus on dynamic or input-aware tuning strategies capable of adapting to variations in system or algorithm state during a tuning session. Such approaches could periodically re-evaluate previously measured configurations to maintain optimal performance under changing conditions.

5.5 Interface Performance

Tuning individual alpaka kernels only results in an overall runtime improvement if the underlying infrastructure does not contribute a significant portion of the total execution time. Therefore, it is important to examine the runtime overhead introduced by the tuning framework. While we did not perform extensive interface optimizations, this overview aims to provide transparency and highlight the current limitations of the framework. By doing so, we aim to inform future improvements and research efforts in this area. To better understand runtime overheads and to separate the different concerns or aspects of the tuning mechanism, we divide the total overhead into five categories or phases. Some of these phases correspond to prolonged execution periods, while others are one-time events that occur only once per program run. Most of these categories can be intuitively derived from the tuning process illustrated in Section 3.2.

Load Whenever a `.toml` file is available, it is loaded using the `toml11` library [85]. This occurs for each session and provides kernel configurations that match the enqueued kernel. This configuration contains already evaluated parameter configurations recorded in a previous session.

Initialize

Although this step typically includes the loading phase, we separate it to better isolate specific concerns. The initialization phase encompasses all one-time setup tasks at the start of the autotuning process including the initialization of the tuning session object (which might be created once for multiple kernel), but additionally establishing the tuning context for a particular kernel, and extracting compile-time or runtime tunables.

Tune

This is the core tuning-process. It involves retrieving configurations from the queue, selecting the appropriate kernel (especially when compile-time parameters are involved), and updating the selected configuration accordingly. It also might launch the strategy interface depending on the state of the queue in order to generate new parameter configurations.

Store

After successfully evaluating all configurations and meeting the global break criteria, the current tuning context is stored in memory as a TOML table. Once the final kernel associated with a shared configuration file is completed, the entire TOML history is written to disk.

Best

Once the tuning is complete and the results have been saved in a file, the best-performing configurations are applied to the current kernel and `FrameSpec`.

To estimate the runtime overhead introduced by our autotuning framework, we measured the cost of the individual components executed for every kernel invocation. Specifically, we timed the `enqueue` call on the tuning session as one timing measurement, and the `enqueue` followed by `wait` issued by alpaka separately, which ultimately launches the kernel on the target accelerator.

The timing measurements for both the tuning and best phases were obtained from the *BabelStream* and *HeatEquation* benchmarks, using all four strategies on the Nvidia H100-SXM5. The dataset comprises 10,000 tuning samples for compile-time variables, along with an example involving up to six independent

Figure 5.9: Runtime overhead distribution across five tuning phases, measured on the Capella Cluster using the two core [0-1] setup, where enqueued alpaka kernels ran on the Nvidia H100-SXM5 GPU (see Section 4.1). Left: Combined overhead measurements from all strategies on the *HeatEquation* and *BabelStream* benchmark for the *Strategy*, *Tune*, and *Best* phases (10000 samples each). The *Init* phase is measured exclusively on the *HeatEquation* benchmark, repeated 50 times. Right: *Load* and *Store* overheads are shown across varying numbers of configurations (based on 20 measurements), also based only on *HeatEquation*. Notice: y-axis is in logarithmic scaling in order to compare separate Phases. Whisker of the boxes extend to 1,5 times the Inter quartile range.

parameters. This variety ensures a fair and representative evaluation, rather than relying on a single, potentially unrepresentative case.

The difference between the two measurements represents the net overhead of the alpaka tuner interface. All timings were taken using `std::chrono::high_resolution_clock` and recorded in nanoseconds. Although this clock does not achieve true nanosecond granularity, our results indicate that we do not observe overheads below a threshold of 100 ns, which is significant enough to be relevant for practical purposes.

The *Init* phase—although it can take up to 5 ms—is a one-time event and is therefore usually negligible. For workflows in which even a single 5 ms delay is unacceptable, autotuning should be disabled altogether. More relevant for online tuning are the *Tune*, and *Best* phases, because they are executed for every kernel launch. While a few extreme outliers exceeding 100 μs occur during the *Tuning* phase, these potentially involved a call to the strategy interface which was very costly, since a new config might not be found in the first iteration, the *maximum* overhead observed for a single kernel is about 2 μs. After the tuning session has finished and the tuning mechanism has entered the *Best* phase there is still a residual overhead because, for example, compile-time parameters require selecting the appropriate kernel template at runtime.

The right panel of Figure 5.9 shows the cost of loading and storing configuration files. We present the number of configurations instead of the TOML file size, as it is the primary parameter that defines the tuner’s workload and is immediately interpretable by the reader. The file size, while roughly proportional, varies with formatting and serialization details. In the current implementation every configuration—including its individual runtimes as well as invalid configurations—is written to a TOML history file. When 16384 configurations have been evaluated, reading this file already takes several *seconds*. Loading is slower than storing because memory allocations are required; moreover the content is first parsed into a TOML tree and then transformed into a map before it is converted into the user-defined parameter objects. A straightforward optimization would be to persist *only* in the best configuration instead of all the history. In Figure 5.10, the timing runtime overhead of tuning phases in which the strategy was invoked is shown. As expected, the exhaustive search approach exhibits the lowest runtime overhead,

Figure 5.10: Runtime overhead of individual tuning strategies, based on the tuning phase runtime Overhead (visible in figure 5.9). The reported results show tuning iterations in which the strategy interface was invoked in the tuning phase. Whisker extend to 1.5 times of the inter-quartile range.

since it is guaranteed to find a new configuration in $O(1)$ time. Strategies that rely on random selection may require multiple attempts to retrieve a new configuration. Among them, random explore shows the largest number of outliers: when the initially sampled configuration is already part of the tuning space, it defaults to exploring configurations using exhaustive search starting from the current configuration. However, unlike exhaustive search—which progresses through the search space in a predictable, linear fashion—random explore must convert a multi-dimensional sampled starting index into a linear space at each iteration. Even then, it may fail to find a new suitable candidate if the next configuration has already been cached from a previous random sample. This occasionally introduces noticeable overhead, as reflected by the rare but pronounced upper whisker in the plot.

The median and interquartile range are highest for simulated annealing, which is expected due to its slightly higher algorithmic and operational intensity. Nonetheless, the increase is modest—roughly double the median overhead of exhaustive search.

Overall, none of the implemented strategies exhibit a significant runtime overhead, with medians in the range of $2\ \mu\text{s}$ to $4\ \mu\text{s}$. For context, the kernels in *HeatEquation* and *BabelStream* typically run on the Nvidia GPU—which produces the lowest runtimes in our test setup—for 2 ms to 5 ms when using the largest evaluated data size of 2 GiB. At this scale, a median tuning overhead of $2\ \mu\text{s}$ to $4\ \mu\text{s}$ is far below 0.2% of the kernel runtime. For smaller problem sizes, this ratio increases: the shortest kernel in the CLUE benchmark (*ComputeHistogram*) runs in $43\ \mu\text{s}$, making a $4\ \mu\text{s}$ tuning overhead nearly 10% of its runtime. However, this kernel accounts for only 3.86% of the total execution time of the benchmark, so its overall impact remains limited. By contrast, a more decisive kernel such as *AssignClusters* runs in 0.379 ms after tuning, with the tuning overhead amounting to only about 1% of its runtime during kernel invocation. It is worth noting that kernels with execution times in the few–tens of microseconds range inherently suffer from poor device utilization, as kernel launch latency (*enqueue*) and device synchronization constitute a significant fraction of the total runtime. Consequently, such kernels are unlikely to yield optimal throughput on modern GPUs, and a tuning overhead of only $2\ \mu\text{s}$ to $4\ \mu\text{s}$ is therefore negligible in most practical scenarios.

5.6 Strategy Comparison

In this section, we discuss the effects of selecting different search strategies. The implementation details are provided in Section 3.4. Figure 5.11 compares multiple strategies on both GPU test systems. The x-axis shows the number of evaluated configurations, while the y-axis represents the best configuration found up to that iteration.

In our comparison, all strategies are evaluated under identical experimental conditions to ensure a fair and generalizable assessment of their convergence behavior. For the Exhaustive Search strategy, we introduce a single random sampling step to determine its initial position in the tuning space. Without this, its performance trajectory would be entirely deterministic for a given benchmark and parameter ordering, which could lead to misleading conclusions: starting in a region close to the optimum would artificially inflate its apparent convergence speed, whereas starting in a poorly performing region could suggest the opposite. In both cases, the outcome would largely reflect the arbitrary ordering of the parameter space and only be strictly tied to this specific benchmark and tuning space, rather than the intrinsic qualities of the strategy itself. Introducing a random initial position mitigates this bias, enabling the results to represent a more realistic range of possible starting conditions and making the comparison with other, inherently stochastic strategies both fairer and more informative.

For each strategy, we plot the median performance across 20 independent runs (solid line) and a shaded area representing the 20%–80% performance range. We selected the *HeatEquation* benchmark for this evaluation because it consistently demonstrated clear performance variation across the tested architectures, allowing strategy differences to be more easily observed. Each strategy was run for 2000 evaluated configurations on both GPU devices.

The results indicate that all random-based strategies rapidly discover configurations with runtimes close to the optimal configuration, whereas Exhaustive Search struggles to improve beyond approximately 120% of the best observed runtime. Its effectiveness largely depends on the starting position and, because exhaustive exploration requires considerable time to traverse higher-dimensional parameters that may enable more favorable, architecture-specific chunk layouts, such configurations can remain unexplored for many iterations. A very large extended percentile area across architectures further underscores this sensitivity, with the effect on the NVIDIA GPU extending even to the top of the chart—indicating that more than 20% of runs did not achieve any improvement over the default configuration within the first 2000 evaluated configurations.

The random-based strategies also reveal that many configurations perform reasonably well: after roughly 750 evaluations, the best runtime improves only gradually, with no major leaps. This suggests a relatively dense cluster of near-optimal configurations. While Exhaustive Search could eventually find these configurations, such improvements could also be expected from a sufficiently long-running Random Explore.

When comparing the random-based methods, the performance differences are generally minor. A small exception is *Random Explore*, for which the 20%–80% percentile area was consistently larger on both architectures, indicating less consistency in convergence speed compared to the other random-based methods. Simulated Annealing did not produce a statistically significant advantage over Random Sample. Sometimes, it achieved marginally better results in the early stages (50–500 configurations), but this is likely due to the abundance of near-optimal configurations in the search space, making it probable for a naive random method to quickly reach a high-performing configuration. On the NVIDIA GPU, Random Sampling even slightly outperformed Simulated Annealing after 2000 configurations, as the annealing temperature by then had decayed enough for the search to become trapped in a local optimum. It should also be noted that we did not perform extensive hyperparameter tuning of Simulated Annealing for this specific benchmark: optimal settings may vary substantially depending on the problem characteristics and the total number of evaluations, which was beyond the scope of this study.

In conclusion, for practical applications, this experiment reinforces that the choice of tuning strategy depends strongly on the dimensionality of the parameter space and the total evaluation budget. When the search space is large and an exhaustive approach would require evaluating millions of configurations, or

Figure 5.11: Comparison of tuning strategies across platforms on the *HeatEquation* stencil kernel. The median tuning process is represented by lines and the shaded area indicates the 20% to 80% percentile for each strategy. Recorded from 20 runs per strategy while evaluating 2000 configurations. See Section 5.3 to inspect the detailed parameter values used.

more precisely, when the ratio of total evaluated configurations to the number of kernel runs performed is high, random or adaptive strategies are generally preferable because they converge more quickly and thus reduce tuning time. It should also be noted that the number of configurations is not equivalent to the number of kernel runs required to satisfy local break criteria. This distinction is important because during the tuning phase suboptimal configurations are executed, which can slow the application and diminish potential gains. The tuning mechanism itself provides several parameters—exposed through environment variables—that can be used to control both the number of configurations Section 3.4 generated and the number of evaluations performed before locking in the best configuration found so far, therefore allowing to influence this ratio. Conversely, when the total number of evaluations is small relative to the number of kernel executions in production, more exhaustive strategies—at least Random Explore—can be justified to reduce the risk of consistently selecting a configuration that is slightly suboptimal (e.g., 1–2%), as such differences can accumulate into substantial performance losses over the lifetime of the application. However, if frequent load changes require repeatedly re-evaluating the current tuning context, a faster-converging method may be preferable to minimize overall runtime overhead. An important open question—reserved for future work—is how runtime behavior shifts when multiple tuning contexts, which utilize the context-switch at runtime via the `sessionSpecifier` mechanism Chapter 3. So far the looked upon kernels (especially BabelStream), do perform context switches but only utilizing compile-time specialization. For example, restricting tuning contexts to particular array sizes or problem characteristics could improve specialization but may also increase overhead (and memory footprint) if switches are frequent.

6 Summary and Future Work

6.1 Summary

This thesis contributes to the field of performance-portable heterogeneous computing by presenting a lightweight autotuning framework integrated into the alpaka C++ programming library (more specifically, into the prototypical successor called alpaka 3). The framework aims to close the gap between portable *code* and portable *performance* through a uniform interface that exposes both kernel-launch and algorithm-specific parameters, which are empirically evaluated at runtime. alpaka offers essential tuning knobs for kernel-launch parameters through back-end-agnostic decomposition (`FrameSpec`) and tunable worker layouts (`ThreadSpec`), which the framework leverages for automated tuning. In addition, support for both algorithm-specific runtime and compile-time parameters can reduce manual tuning effort, while providing the interface to enforce correctness when dealing with algorithmic constraints. The goal is to achieve near-optimal configurations across vendors and problem sizes with minimal code modifications. In contrast to classical autotuning approaches such as [19, 18], which operate as external tools, this work embeds autotuning directly into the alpaka programming model. Although it may not provide the full range of utilities and strategies found in mature, standalone frameworks (see Section 2.8), its integration into alpaka allows tuning to be performed transparently across all supported back-ends without breaking the single-source, performance-portable programming paradigm. By leveraging alpaka’s existing abstractions, tuning can be carried out during production runs with minimal overhead 5.5, transforming performance portability from a manual, tool-dependent process into a built-in capability of the application’s primary execution layer.

After providing the theoretical background in Section 2.1—including several forms of parallelism [21] and their role in overcoming the Power Wall [26]—we examined the architectures of our test systems in Sections 2.2,2.3,2.4: an AMD EPYC 9334 CPU (Zen 4) [37, 38, 39], an NVIDIA H100-SXM5 GPU (Hopper) [44], and an AMD RX 7900 XTX GPU (RDNA 3) [48, 49]. We related their execution hierarchies, memory organizations, and concurrency mechanisms to programming abstractions in CUDA, HIP, and OpenMP, establishing the foundation for the autotuning approach in alpaka described in the following sections.

Afterwards, we examined alpaka in detail (see Section 2.5). In doing so, this thesis provides the first comprehensive overview of the new alpaka 3 programming model [11]. We focused on concepts such as the separation between frame specifications and thread specifications, which enable a hardware-agnostic yet tunable decomposition of workloads. We showed how the mapping of workers to frame elements corresponds both to native API constructs and to the underlying architectural components identified earlier, ensuring that hardware resources are abstracted without losing the ability to optimize their use. Through alpaka’s back-end-specific APIs, these characteristics are expressed as portable abstractions, forming a set of parameters that can later be tuned for performance.

Finally, we provided a theoretical description of autotuning and reviewed a selection of established strategies, ranging from exhaustive and random search to a more sophisticated approach in the form of simulated annealing 2.7. Before turning to our own design and results, this thesis offered an extensive review of the existing literature, organizing prior work along four main dimensions: execution requirement (static vs. empirical), execution stage (runtime adjustments vs. source code transformations), tuning environment (online vs. offline), and optimization strategy (search-based vs. model-based). We discussed the respective strengths and limitations of these categories and how they frame the trade-offs faced by both contemporary and classical work in the autotuning domain.

With the background established, we presented the design and implementation of the proposed tuning framework (Chapter 3), built around four goals: seamless alpaka integration, support for runtime

and compile-time parameters, explicit tuning-context management, and robust noise handling. The tuning context uniquely identified a session by kernel, device, environment, and metric, enabling reuse of measurements across experiments. The framework provided an accessible interface for online and offline tuning of alpaka components (`numFrames`, `frameExtent`, `numBlocks`, `numThreads`), algorithm-specific parameters, and compile-time options (Section 3.3), supporting constraints, strategy selection, and control of search-space size (Section 3.5). To handle noise on shared HPC systems, we applied CI-based break criteria, early rejection of suboptimal configurations via the Kruskal–Wallis test, and a configuration queue to limit bias from transient system states (Section 3.4).

The evaluation part 5 began with a Poisson equation solver, demonstrating the framework’s ability to handle user-defined runtime parameters. This experiment also showed that, even with the current interface—tightly coupled to alpaka’s `enqueue` method—we can optimize arbitrary functions by defining an alpaka kernel on the host. This highlights the framework’s versatility, as we are not limited to executing kernels on a device; with the proper annotations, any function or software subsystem could be expressed as a host-side kernel.

The following three benchmarks offered distinct perspectives on the proposed framework. For *BabelStream*, a widely recognized open-source memory-bandwidth-bound workload, the results confirmed that when kernel performance is constrained primarily by DRAM bandwidth, only minimal speedups are attainable. For small problem sizes near cache boundaries, noise effects further obscured consistent gains. However, *BabelStream* served as a valuable case study, demonstrating the support of the framework for compile-time parameters (SIMD concurrency), which produced measurable differences in some configurations. While outcomes varied across architectures, tuning potential was ultimately mostly limited by hardware constraints.

By contrast, the *HeatEquation* benchmark, with higher arithmetic intensity (while still being memory-bound), revealed a clear set of influential parameters. High-performing configurations aligned closely with each device’s architectural characteristics: the AMD GPU achieved substantial speedups, the NVIDIA GPU saw moderate but consistent gains, and the CPU backend showed only limited improvement.

The final benchmark, CLUE [96] (Section 5.4), showcased the tuner’s ability to optimize a complex, multi-kernel workload. Here, tuning was applied in a largely black-box fashion, focusing on Thread-Spec parameters. Heatmap analyses of the tuning spaces revealed that one kernel—`AssignClusters`—dominated runtime. Initially over-subscribed with an excessive number of blocks, yielding a $\sim 2\times$ speedup for that kernel alone. Other kernels, such as `ComputeLocalDensity` and `ComputeDistanceToHigher`, achieved smaller but still notable improvements of up to 20% over their defaults.

Overall, these results illustrated that tuning can deliver substantial gains when the architecture permits, and that incorporating domain knowledge or algorithm-specific parameters can amplify these benefits. This is obviously not guaranteed—outcomes depend heavily on the workload, hardware, and benchmark characteristics discussed above—but even in less favorable cases, the framework provides a far easier and more systematic path to exploration than manual tuning.

An interesting part was assessing the generalizability of tuned configurations. We evaluated how well the optimal parameters from one tuning session transferred to another session using a different input ordering but the same algorithmic problem. The results showed that, in the worst case, performance gains could diminish significantly—by up to 30%—when the *best*-configuration from one input-dataset, was applied to a different input-dataset. These findings indicated that the tuning framework must account for changing workloads and system states a consideration that warrants in-depth investigation in future work.

Recognizing that the performance of individual benchmarks, is not a sufficient measure of the tuner’s overall utility, we also evaluated its net impact on total runtime across all benchmarks. The analysis showed that, for all implemented strategies, the tuner’s overhead—excluding I/O operations for loading or storing the tuning history to disk—remained small relative to kernel execution time in workloads with meaningful runtimes Section 5.5.

Separately, we compared the implemented search strategies. Random methods generally converged toward near-optimal configurations more quickly, whereas exhaustive evaluation required longer exploration phases. In contrast to some reports in the literature (for example [19]), we did not observe a decisive advantage for more advanced strategies in this setting, with respect to the convergence speed; while further hyperparameter tuning might change this outcome, simpler methods better support the project’s overarching goal of delivering performance portability out-of-the-box with minimal user intervention. We also noted that running suboptimal configurations—whether due to early termination, strategy limitations, or changing execution conditions—can have lasting effects on overall application performance (Section 5.6).

In conclusion, the autotuning framework presented in this thesis delivers a tightly integrated, architecture-aware solution for performance optimization in alpaka-based applications. The current implementation serves as a baseline, providing developers with an accessible yet powerful tool to achieve high levels of performance portability in heterogeneous HPC environments, without the need for manual tuning or extensive profiling. Experimental results demonstrate the framework’s ability to deliver meaningful speedups for relevant workload sizes, while respecting architectural constraints, maintaining a minimal runtime footprint for typical kernel durations, and achieving convergence speeds suitable for online tuning scenarios.

6.2 Future Work

Implementation-wise, this project is in a prototype stage. Its flexible, configurable design leaves considerable room for optimization and the addition of new features. The following directions build on this foundation: Some arise directly from limitations and observations made in the results, while others are motivated by opportunities to broaden applicability and improve robustness.

The first direction is a controlled study of *noise-robust evaluation* and the *configuration queue* (Section 3.4). Such a study should quantify the queue’s impact on false-positive and false-negative classifications under realistic noise patterns, including frequency scaling, thermal throttling, and rescheduling. Parameters such as queue length and interleave depth could be varied, with comparisons between fixed-repeat and confidence-interval-driven stopping criteria.

Another closely related aspect is the *generalizability* of tuned configurations. As discussed in Section 6.1, optimal parameters from one input ordering can lose a substantial share of their performance advantage when applied to a different ordering of the same algorithmic problem. Addressing this sensitivity will require mechanisms for adaptive re-tuning or re-evaluation to maintain performance across changing workloads and system states, the details and benefits of such an approach will ultimately depend on the application’s usage patterns and workflows.

A next step toward a more complete framework is the integration of more *sophisticated, model-based, and adaptive strategies*. Beyond the current search-based approaches, this could potentially include time-varying Bayesian optimization [93] to address performance drift, as well as multi-armed bandits for dynamic strategy selection ([94]). However, while the literature demonstrates clear benefits for these approaches in specific contexts, our experiments did not show a substantial improvement in convergence speed or overall performance from adopting more sophisticated strategies.

Further optimizations could include *constraint space pruning*, transitioning from lazy constraint checks to constraint graphs or trees that eliminate invalid combinations early [92], which would make strategies more robust and easier to implement.

Persistence mechanisms could be improved by adopting compact binary or database-backed formats—other options include storing only the best-so-far or Pareto-optimal parameter-configurations per context (Section 5.5).

The current metric interface (Section 3.5) was used exclusively with execution-time measurements. Future extensions could leverage the same interface to track additional metrics—such as energy consumption, hardware occupancy, or combined performance–efficiency measures—and analyze their impact on tuning outcomes or analyze the impact of tuning on other back-ends and devices including SYCL/Intel

GPUs and FPGAs.

Scaling the tuner to large-scale HPC simulations or at least analyzing its effects and potential gains in large-scale simulation is also essential. This could involve multi-node and multi-GPU deployments with mixed back-ends.

Together, these directions aim to evolve the proposed framework into an even more noise-resilient, adaptive, and scalable tuning system, capable of delivering consistent performance gains across architectures, problem sizes, and dynamic execution environments.

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A Appendix - Detailed Benchmark Settings

Tuning landscape - relative performance visualization formula

This section provides additional explanations on and context how the relative performance measurements for individual tuning parameters presented in figures 5.2 and 5.4 are calculated. Using the formalism from 2.7, let

$$T(v, j) = \{C \in T \mid C_j = v\}$$

be the set of configurations where the j -th parameter equals v . The plotted quantity is

$$R(v, j) = \frac{\min_{C \in T(v, j)} m_K(C)}{m_K(C_{\text{default}})},$$

where m_K is the measurement function and C_{default} the default configuration from the native *BabelStream* benchmark. Here $R > 1$ indicates improvement, $R < 1$ indicates slowdown.

Default parameters.

Several Benchmarks conducted in Chapter 5 compare their results to a default configuration. This default configuration is what was used in the original version of alpaka. In most of the cases, these default configurations represent an already optimized (especially with respect to thread-block size) set of parameters derived by the NVIDIA or architecture specific guidelines and profiling tools such as the Nsight Compute CLI [103].

Table A.1: Default parameters. A dash (—) denotes that the tuning parameter is not used by the kernel.

Benchmark Kernel(s)	Architecture	concurrent- Elements	frameExtent	numBlocks	numThreads
BabelStream Add, Copy Mult, Triad	CPU – EPYC 9334	16	—	65536	—
	GPU – RX 7900 XTX	16	—	65536	512
	GPU – H100-SXM5	8	—	131072	512
BabelStream Dot	CPU – EPYC 9334	16	512	1024	—
	GPU – RX 7900 XTX	16	512	1024	512
	GPU – H100-SXM5	8	512	1024	512
HeatEquation Stencil	CPU – EPYC 9334	—	x: 16, y: 16	x: 1024, y: 1024	x: —, y: —
	GPU – RX 7900 XTX	—	x: 16, y: 16	x: 1024, y: 1024	x: 16, y: 16
	GPU – H100-SXM5	—	x: 16, y: 16	x: 1024, y: 1024	x: 16, y: 16

NumBlocks

As mentioned in Section 3.3 the number of thread-block’s, which gets selected by the tuning framework on default, depends on a hardware characteristic called number of multiprocessors, which gets provided by alpaka and the number of available frames.

Number of Multiprocessors across hardware devices, which are relevant for Chapter 5. :

- **CPU – AMD EPYC™ 9334** for CPU architectures this retrieves the number of physical cores. This is 64 (see Section 2.2) since it is a dual socket system, but unfortunately in the experimental

setup only **56** out of the 64 cores where permitted (some system restrictions enforced by slurm). Therefore we manually set the number of multiprocessors for the CPU back-end to 56.

- **GPU – AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX** corresponds to the number of dual compute units: **48** (see Section 2.4).
- **GPU – NVIDIA H100-SXM5** corresponds to the number of multiprocessors: **132** (2.3).

This resource gets partitioned across dimensions and used as a stride to construct a linear tuning space, which contains multiple of this resource. The stride itself might already be a multiple of that resource in order to satisfy a maximum number of values for this tuning parameter. Figure A.2 shows the concrete values for the `numBlocks` tuning parameter across benchmarks and corresponding kernel invocations. It is important to note that not all kernel invocations used the default `NumBlocksTune` setting, as custom values were also permitted—particularly in the case of . . . and . . . within the **CLUE** benchmark. Since the upper bound for `NumBlocksTune` is determined by the number of frames, which typically corresponds to the array size, we also report the associated `arraySize` alongside the corresponding kernel where applicable.

Table A.2: Number of thread-block’s (parameter: `numBlocks`) for each kernel across different architectures. The notation “ $a, 2a, \dots, na$ ” represents a linear sequence defined by $i \cdot a$, where a is the step size and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is an integer index.

Benchmark	Kernel	Architecture		
		AMD EPYC™ 9334	AMD Radeon RX 7900 XTX	NVIDIA H100-SXM5
BabelStream	Add, Copy, Dot, Mult, Triad			
	ArraySize = 2 GiB	[56, 2×56, ..., 8×56]	[512×48, 1024×48, ..., 10752×48]	[128×132, 256×132, ..., 3968×132]
HeatEquation	Stencil	x = [8, 16, ..., 56, 512]	x = [64, 128, ..., 512]	x = [60, 120, ..., 480, 512]
	buffer-size = 2 GiB	y = [7, 14, ..., 49, 512]	y = [60, 120, ..., 480, 512]	y = [55, 110, ..., 495, 512]

Nsight Compute Profiling Methodology for Reported Percentages

The percentages of throughput reported in this thesis in Section 5.2 are derived from hardware-level profiling and are not directly comparable to the wall-clock performance measurements presented in the main text. Specifically, NVIDIA Nsight Compute 2025.1.0.0 was used to collect the metric `dram_throughput.avg.pct_` during isolated kernel execution, using the same launch parameters as in the tuned configurations for the array-size = 2048 GiB. This metric reports the ratio of achieved DRAM throughput to Nsight Compute’s internally defined sustained peak for the device, measured only over the active execution time of the kernel. As such, the percentages reflect the utilization of the memory subsystem under idealized conditions and exclude host queue latency and device synchronization overhead. In contrast, the bandwidth percentages calculated from the measurements presented in Figure 5.3 include these overheads, making it more difficult to accurately assess proximity to the ultimate hardware constraints. This is why a Nsight Compute profile was used for this analysis.

Glossary

alpaka alpaka - Abstraction Library for Parallel Kernel Acceleration [10]. 3–5, 15, 16, 18, 73

alpaka alpaka 3 - Abstraction Library for Parallel Kernel Acceleration. This is referring to the successor of alpaka. At the time of writing this thesis, alpaka 3 was in a prototype stage [11]. alpaka 3 is commonly referred to as just alpaka from section 2.5 onwards. 3, 4, 11, 15–23, 31, 33, 37–40, 46, 49, 50, 52, 54, 64, 68, 69, 73–75, 85–87, 89, 91, 92

ATF A Generic Auto-Tuning Framework, a generic framework for autotuning using Cpp. 31

ATLAS Automatically Tuned Linear Algebra Software, a library that uses empirical autotuning for performance 27–30

CHILL Compiler-High-Level Loop Library, a framework for source-to-source loop transformation and autotuning 27

CU Compute Unit, the fundamental hardware unit for parallel execution on AMD GPUs, functionally similar to NVIDIA's Streaming Multiprocessors (SMs) 15, 61

CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture, NVIDIA's parallel computing platform 3–5, 13–19, 27–31, 33, 50, 54, 73, 85

FPGA Field-Programmable Gate Array, reconfigurable hardware used for specialized computation 3

frameExtent Number of elements in a Frame. Parameter introduced by alpaka as part of the FrameSpec. 17, 18, 22, 35, 45, 54, 55, 59–61, 74, 89

Frames A *frame* is a logical subset of indices defined by the FrameSpec. The amount of indices of a frame is described by the frameExtent. These indices corresponds to a subregion of the overall problem domain and are usually processed by a single thread-block. While each frame is mapped to exactly one block, a thread-block may process multiple frames. 59, 61

FrameSpec Frame Specification, an alpaka abstraction, which can be used to describe the index-space. It contains the numFrames and frameExtent parameters. It also contains the ThreadSpec. 18, 22, 35, 39, 46, 54, 64, 65, 68, 73, 91, 92

HIP Heterogeneous-Compute Interface for Portability, AMD's GPU programming model 3–5, 15, 16, 18, 19, 33, 50, 73

HPC High-Performance Computing 3, 6, 27–31, 76

KTT Kernel Tuning Toolkit, a framework for autotuning OpenCL and CUDA kernels 30, 31

LS-CAT Large-Scale CUDA AutoTuning dataset, a benchmark set for kernel performance tuning and machine learning 28

MPI Message Passing Interface 7, 8, 28, 31

- numBlocks** Number of thread-block's. In the context of alpaka it refers to a parameter in the ThreadSpec. This parameter has a different meaning, depending on the underlying execution back-end. For more detail see table 2.2 18, 35, 40, 45, 55, 56, 61, 64, 65, 74, 87, 89, 90
- numFrames** Number of Frames. Parameter introduced by alpaka as part of the FrameSpec. 17, 18, 35, 45, 74
- numThreads** Number of threads in a thread-block. In the context of alpaka it refers to a parameter in the ThreadSpec. This parameter has a different meaning, depending on the underlying execution back-end. For more detail see table 2.2 18, 20, 35, 45, 54–56, 61, 64, 74, 85, 89
- nvcc** NVIDIA CUDA Compiler, a compiler driver for CUDA source files 3
- OpenCL** Open Computing Language, a open-standard for writing cross platform platform parallel programs 29–31
- OpenMP** Open Multi-Processing, API for shared-memory parallelism 5, 7, 11, 13, 15, 18, 19, 28, 30, 33, 49, 50, 73
- SIMD** Single instruction multiple data (elements) 7, 15, 22, 23, 38, 55
- SIMT** Single instruction multiple threads, parallelization mostly present on Nvidia GPU's 7
- SM** Streaming Multiprocessor, the fundamental parallel compute unit in NVIDIA GPUs, responsible for executing threads in groups called warps 12–15
- SYCL** Standard C++ for Heterogeneous Computing, widely adopted and integrated in Intel's oneAPI ecosystems 4, 5, 15, 18, 19
- thread-block** In the context of alpaka it refers to an abstraction called thread-block. This abstraction has a different meaning, depending on the underlying execution back-end. For more detail see table 2.2. The terminology closely matches CUDA's terminology. 3, 18, 19, 61, 64, 65, 86, 87, 89–92
- ThreadSpec** Thread specification, contains the number thread-blocks and the number of threads. The terminology of the ThreadSpec closely matches CUDA's terminology. To contextualize the meaning of the Thread specification on individual execution back-ends see table 2.2. 17, 18, 39, 40, 54, 73, 74, 87, 91, 92
- ytopt** Yet Another Tuning Optimization Tool, an online autotuning framework using Bayesian optimization 28, 30, 31

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